

Ostbayerische Technische Hochschule Amberg-Weiden
Fakultät Elektrotechnik, Medien und Informatik

Studiengang Künstliche Intelligenz

Masterarbeit

von

Martin Zizler

**Globale Multi-Cloud-Strategien: Effiziente Nutzung von
AWS und Alibaba Cloud für skalierbare
Cloud-Anwendungen**

Global Multi-Cloud Strategies: Efficient Utilization of AWS
and Alibaba Cloud for Scalable Cloud Applications

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Globale Multi-Cloud-Strategien: Effiziente Nutzung von AWS und Alibaba Cloud für skalierbare Cloud-Anwendungen

Zusammenfassung:

Diese Arbeit untersucht Strategien zur Ermöglichung skalierbarer, sicherer und compliance-konformer Anwendungen in einer globalen Multi-Cloud-Umgebung durch die Integration von Amazon Web Services und Alibaba Cloud. Während sich die bestehende Forschung überwiegend auf generische Multi-Cloud-Architekturen konzentriert, wurde den Interoperabilitäts Herausforderungen zwischen AWS und Alibaba Cloud, die für Unternehmen mit Aktivitäten in westlichen und chinesischen Märkten entscheidend sind, bislang wenig Aufmerksamkeit geschenkt. Die Arbeit verwendet einen vergleichenden Analyseansatz, um Infrastruktur, Serviceportfolios, APIs und Sicherheitsmodelle beider Anbieter zu evaluieren. Auf Basis dieser Erkenntnisse wird eine Referenzarchitektur entworfen und durch eine Proof-of-Concept-Bereitstellung einer repräsentativen Workload validiert. Die Evaluation zeigt Abwägungen in Bezug auf Portabilität, Kosten, Leistung und Sicherheit auf und leitet daraus praxisnahe Empfehlungen für Praktikerinnen und Praktiker ab. Diese Arbeit liefert eine strukturierte Methodik sowie eine validierte Strategie für Organisationen, die AWS und Alibaba Cloud in Kombination nutzen möchten.

Schlüsselwörter: Multi-Cloud, AWS, Alibaba Cloud, Interoperability, Infrastructure-as-Code, Cloud Strategy

Abstract

This thesis investigates strategies for enabling scalable, secure, and compliant applications in a global multi-cloud environment by integrating Amazon Web Services and Alibaba Cloud. While existing research has focused primarily on generic multi-cloud architectures, little attention has been paid to the interoperability challenges between AWS and Alibaba Cloud, which are critical for enterprises operating across Western and Chinese markets. The thesis employs a comparative analysis framework to evaluate infrastructure, service portfolios, APIs, and security models of both providers. Based on these insights, a reference architecture is designed and validated through a proof-of-concept deployment of a representative workload. The evaluation demonstrates trade-offs in portability, cost, performance, and security, offering practical recommendations for practitioners. This work contributes a structured methodology and validated strategy for organizations aiming to leverage AWS and Alibaba Cloud in tandem.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Motivation	2
1.2	Problem statement	2
1.3	Research Objectives	3
1.4	Structure of the Thesis	3
2	State of the Art	6
2.1	Overview of Cloud Computing	6
2.1.1	History and Evolution	6
2.1.2	Rise of Multi-Cloud Strategies	7
2.2	Distinguishing Multi-Cloud from Related Concepts	8
2.3	Challenges in Multi-Cloud Migration	9
2.3.1	Interoperability Challenges	9
2.3.2	Security and Compliance Challenges	10
2.3.3	Performance and Cost Optimization Challenges	11
2.4	Best Practices in Cloud Infrastructure Portability	11
2.4.1	Use of Abstraction Layers and Middleware	12
2.4.2	Infrastructure as Code and Cloud Development Kits	12
2.4.3	Security Best Practices	14
2.4.4	Monitoring and Performance Management	15
2.5	Emerging Trends and Research Gaps	17
3	Research Methodology	19
3.1	Methodological Approach	19
3.2	Comparative Analysis Framework	19
3.3	Multi-Cloud Strategy Development	21
3.4	Deployment Steps	22
3.5	Evaluation Methodology	22
3.6	Summary	23
4	AWS vs. Alibaba Cloud: A Comparative Analysis	24
4.1	Global Infrastructure & Reach	24
4.2	Core Service Portfolio	25
4.3	APIs & Automation	30
4.3.1	API Models and Differences	30

4.3.2	Infrastructure-as-Code Tooling	31
4.4	General Security & Identity	32
4.5	Regulatory & Data Sovereignty	34
4.5.1	China-Specific Regulatory Environment	34
4.5.2	Regional Privacy Frameworks	35
4.6	Key Trade-offs	35
5	Design of the Multi-Cloud Strategy	37
5.1	Scope, Goals, and Design Drivers	37
5.2	Reference Compute Models	38
5.3	Target State and Guiding Principles	39
5.4	Architecture Design for AWS–Alibaba Cloud Interoperability	40
5.5	Infrastructure as Code: Tooling and Migration Design	43
5.6	Security and Compliance Strategy for Multi-Cloud Workloads	44
5.7	Deployment Models and Patterns	46
5.8	Risks and Mitigations	47
5.9	Summary	48
6	Proof-of-Concept Implementation	49
6.1	Representative Workload and Reference Architecture	49
6.2	Implementation on AWS	54
6.3	Implementation on Alibaba Cloud	54
6.4	Portability and Migration Effort	55
6.5	Basic Validation: Functionality, Security, and Logging	55
6.6	Step-by-Step Deployment Guide	55
6.7	Alternative Deployment: CDK for Terraform	61
6.8	Certificate Handling and Key Management	63
6.9	Teardown and Cost Hygiene	65
6.10	Summary	65
7	Evaluation and Optimization	67
7.1	Introduction	67
7.2	Evaluation Criteria and Methodology	68
7.3	Portability and Expressiveness	69
7.4	Performance Analysis	72
7.5	Cost Analysis	72
7.6	Security and Compliance	74
7.7	Operational Complexity and Maintainability	74
7.8	Optimization Opportunities	75
7.9	Trade-Offs and Lessons Learned	76
7.10	Recommendations for Practitioners	76
7.11	Summary and Outlook	78
8	Conclusion	79
8.1	Summary of Key Findings	79
8.2	Reflections on Research Contribution	80

8.3	Concluding Remarks	81
9	Future Work	82
9.1	Limitations of the Study	82
9.2	Future Research Directions	83
9.3	Closing Perspective	83
	Acknowledgements	84
	Bibliography	85
	List of Figures	98
	List of Tables	99

Chapter 1

Introduction

Cloud computing has revolutionized the way businesses manage and deploy IT infrastructure, providing scalable, on-demand access to computing resources. Organizations around the world rely on different cloud service providers (CSP) to support their applications and services. Amazon Web Services (AWS) has established itself as a leader in the cloud computing market and is the oldest and most widely adopted CSP, as seen in figure 1.1. The over 200 fully featured services from data centers around the world often make it the first choice for companies [1]. In contrast, Alibaba Cloud holds the position as the current market leader in China, driven by its extensive local infrastructure and wide-ranging services [2]. Given its dominant market position and importance in the Chinese cloud ecosystem, Alibaba Cloud was chosen for this thesis to examine multi-cloud strategies involving both global and regional market leaders.

Figure 1.1: Worldwide market share of leading cloud service providers in Q4 of 2024 [3]

As businesses expand globally, they frequently face regional cloud preferences or regulatory requirements that require the use of alternative providers [4]. This leads many international enterprises to adopt a multi-cloud approach that integrates other CSPs, such as the Chinese Alibaba Cloud.

This thesis explores strategies on how to implement such an approach by highlighting

a specific workload utilizing AWS and Alibaba Cloud. That encompasses approaches on how to overcome several technical challenges, including differences in service architectures, networking, security models, and regulatory requirements.

1.1 Motivation

In today's landscape, cloud computing plays a crucial role in the infrastructure of global enterprises. One key reason for this is the increasing need of computational and storage devices [5]. While cloud computing can broadly be defined as remote access to computing resources [6], modern public cloud service providers (CSPs) offer far more than basic compute and storage. Their platforms now encompass advanced services ranging from machine learning to Internet of Things (IoT) and global-scale content delivery, fundamentally transforming how enterprises design IT systems. This expansion of capabilities underscores the need for multi-cloud strategies that move beyond basic infrastructure outsourcing.

According to Mell et al. [7], there are five essential qualities that make today's cloud providers so useful to consumers. The first one is that a consumer can unilaterally provision computing capabilities automatically (on-demand self-service). The capabilities are also easily available over the network (broad network access). What is also important is that the provider's computing resources are pooled to serve multiple consumers with dynamic assignments (resource pooling). There is also elastic provisioning, which helps to rapidly scale outward and inward depending on demand (rapid elasticity). Last but not least there is extensive monitoring providing transparency for both the provider and the consumer (measured service). These aspects make cloud computing so attractive to businesses. Additionally, they typically also don't need any up-front investment, offer a lower operating cost and reduce business risk [6], [8].

In a global setting, a well-defined multi-cloud approach can go even further beyond by allowing businesses to leverage the strengths of multiple cloud providers. This can help with reducing the risks of vendor lock-in (when the client becomes dependent on the provider) or allowing for regional preferences [9], [10]. However, achieving seamless interoperability between different cloud environments remains a significant challenge [11].

1.2 Problem statement

Organizations operating globally require cloud solutions that support flexibility, security, and compliance across different regions. While AWS is a dominant player in the cloud market, businesses expanding into China often need to adopt Chinese cloud providers due to preferences and market conditions. There are several key challenges:

1. Differences in **cloud architectures**, **APIs**, and **service offerings** between AWS and Alibaba Cloud [5].

2. Ensuring **interoperability** and **portability** of workloads between the two platforms [12], [13].
3. Maintaining **security** and **compliance** standards across cloud environments with different regulatory frameworks [4], [14].
4. Optimizing **cost** and **performance** in a multi-cloud setup [15].
5. Universal monitoring solutions [16].

Existing research on multi-cloud strategies has largely concentrated on conceptual frameworks or high-level architectural issues [5]. However, there is a lack of dedicated empirical studies that address provider-specific integrations, particularly between AWS and Alibaba Cloud. This gap is critical, as enterprises expanding into China must often complement existing AWS deployments with Chinese cloud providers like Alibaba Cloud to meet regulatory, performance, or market requirements. This thesis seeks to close this gap by developing and validating strategies for AWS-Alibaba Cloud interoperability.

1.3 Research Objectives

The primary objective of this thesis is to develop a framework for implementing AWS workloads in Alibaba Cloud while ensuring scalability, security, and efficiency. The specific goals include:

1. Analyzing the key differences between AWS and Alibaba Cloud in terms of architecture, services, and APIs.
2. Identifying interoperability challenges and strategies for workload portability.
3. Designing a scalable multi-cloud architecture that facilitates seamless operation across both platforms.
4. Developing best practices for secure and efficient cloud application deployment in AWS and Alibaba Cloud.
5. Implementing a proof-of-concept (PoC) to validate the proposed strategy.

1.4 Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is structured into three primary parts, made up of nine chapters in total. A general overview of this layout can be seen in 1.2.

Part I: Prologue

The prologue establishes the theoretical background and context for the research. It consists of two chapters:

- **Chapter 1: Introduction**

This chapter introduces the research topic by outlining the significance of cloud

Figure 1.2: Thesis Structure

computing in modern IT environments and the growing adoption of multi-cloud strategies. It presents the motivation behind the research and frames the problem statement, objectives, and scope of the thesis.

- **Chapter 2: State of the Art**

This chapter provides a literature review that delves into existing research on cloud computing, multi-cloud strategies, workload migration, interoperability, and security. It identifies key trends, challenges, and best practices while highlighting research gaps that this thesis aims to address.

Part II: Multi-Cloud Strategy

The core of the thesis focuses on developing and evaluating a multi-cloud strategy for integrating AWS and Alibaba Cloud. This part contains five chapters:

- **Chapter 3: Research Methodology**

This chapter details the research approach and methodology adopted to achieve the thesis objectives. It explains the framework used to conduct a comparative analysis of AWS and Alibaba Cloud, outlines the criteria for selecting representative use cases and workloads, and describes the implementation and evaluation process for the proof-of-concept (PoC).

- **Chapter 4: Comparative Analysis**

This chapter provides an in-depth comparison of AWS and Alibaba Cloud, examining key aspects such as infrastructure, APIs, networking, storage, compute services, security models, and compliance requirements. The comparative analysis lays the groundwork for designing an effective multi-cloud strategy by identifying differences and potential interoperability challenges between the two platforms.

- **Chapter 5: Strategy Development**

Based on the findings from the comparative analysis, this chapter proposes

a strategic framework for integrating AWS and Alibaba Cloud. It explores architectural design options, deployment models (such as containerization or serverless), best practices for ensuring security and compliance, and solutions for workload portability and performance optimization.

- **Chapter 6: Proof-of-Concept Implementation**

This chapter demonstrates the practical application of the presented multi-cloud strategy by implementing a representative workload on AWS and migrating it to Alibaba Cloud. It details the deployment process, the challenges encountered, and the techniques used to address those challenges, with a focus on maintaining interoperability, performance, and security across both cloud environments.

- **Chapter 7: Evaluation**

This chapter evaluates the results of the proof-of-concept implementation by comparing performance, cost, scalability, and security metrics for the AWS and Alibaba Cloud deployments. It assesses the effectiveness of the offered multi-cloud strategy and provides recommendations for businesses seeking to implement similar solutions.

Part III: Epilogue

The epilogue concludes the thesis by summarizing the key findings, discussing the limitations of the study, and suggesting directions for future research:

- **Chapter 9: Conclusion**

This chapter summarizes the main contributions of the thesis, reflecting on how the research objectives were met and emphasizing the practical implications of the presented multi-cloud strategy.

- **Chapter 8: Future Work**

The final chapter explores potential areas for further research on multi-cloud strategies and AWS-Alibaba Cloud interoperability. It discusses emerging trends in cloud computing and outlines opportunities for improving workload migration, security, and automation in multi-cloud environments.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

This chapter presents an overview of cloud computing and multi-cloud strategies, discussing key concepts, challenges, best practices, and emerging trends relevant to workload migration and multi-cloud interoperability.

2.1 Overview of Cloud Computing

This section gives a quick look into the history of cloud computing and the rise of multi-cloud strategies.

2.1.1 History and Evolution

The idea behind cloud computing has already been envisioned as providing computing resources to the public as a utility in the 1960s. This was originally referred to as "computer public utility" [17]. The term "cloud" also has a history of being used in various contexts like describing large ATM networks in the 1990s, but it was Google's CEO Eric Schmidt who popularized the term by using it to describe the business model of providing services across the Internet in 2006 [8].

Nowadays, there are three cloud computing service models that are the industry standards: Software as a Service (SaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) [6]. They can also be seen in figure 2.1.

1. **Infrastructure as a Service** refers to the model in which Cloud Service Providers use virtualization to partition computing resources such as processing power and storage capacity into discrete units. These resources can be dynamically scaled and allocated as needed, allowing customers to deploy and manage their own software [18].
2. **Platform as a Service** goes a step further and doesn't just provide resources but also a software platform where systems run on. An example of this is the Google App Engine [18].

3. **Software as a Service** refers to applications that are provided on-demand over the Internet [8].

Beyond that there are also the newer kind of service models called **Backend as a Service** (BaaS) and **Function as a Service** (FaaS) [19]. These come into play when serverless computing with an event-driven approach is wanted. This will be expanded upon in subsection 2.5.

Figure 2.1: The different cloud computing service models [8]

2.1.2 Rise of Multi-Cloud Strategies

The adoption of multi-cloud strategies has gained momentum in recent years as organizations seek to address key challenges and maximize the benefits of cloud computing. Unlike single-cloud deployments, which rely on a single cloud service provider (CSP), multi-cloud strategies involve leveraging multiple CSPs to enhance flexibility, resilience, and performance [20]. This section explores the primary factors driving the rise of multi-cloud strategies and highlights how these factors are relevant to the integration of AWS and Alibaba Cloud, which is central to this thesis.

Vendor Lock-In Reduction

A primary driver for adopting multi-cloud strategies is the mitigation of vendor lock-in [21]. Reliance on a single CSP may restrict flexibility due to proprietary APIs and service models, thereby constraining long-term adaptability. By distributing workloads across AWS and Alibaba Cloud, enterprises can reduce dependency on a single provider and also gain strategic leverage in cost negotiations and technology adoption. However, achieving this distribution introduces interoperability challenges, which this thesis aims to systematically address.

Regional Regulations and Compliance

Global organizations must also navigate varying regulatory environments when deploying cloud-based services across different regions. Laws such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe and China's Cybersecurity Law impose strict data sovereignty and compliance requirements, which may limit where data can be stored or processed. A multi-cloud strategy enables businesses to address these regulatory challenges by selecting CSPs that operate within specific jurisdictions [4]. For instance, a company expanding into China may adopt Alibaba Cloud to comply with local regulations while continuing to use AWS in other regions. This AWS-Alibaba Cloud integration allows the organization to maintain compliance without compromising on performance or scalability.

Global Performance Optimization and Disaster Recovery

Multi-cloud strategies also enhance global performance by enabling organizations to deploy workloads closer to end users in different regions and data centers. This can reduce latency and improve the user experience, particularly for applications with global user bases [22], [23], but Wu et al. [24] also notes that this effect is likely challenging in practice as there can be fluctuations between different cloud services. Additionally, distributing workloads across multiple clouds enhances disaster recovery and business continuity by providing redundancy. If one CSP experiences an outage or performance degradation, the organization can seamlessly failover to another provider, minimizing downtime and data loss [25], [26].

Increased Flexibility in Workload Distribution

Multi-cloud environments offer greater flexibility in workload distribution, allowing organizations to optimize resource allocation based on cost, performance, and specific use case requirements [27]. For example, an organization might choose to distribute workloads and data to different CSPs based on cost and availability, like it was explored in [28]. This flexibility is particularly relevant to this thesis, which focuses on developing strategies for deploying and managing workloads across AWS and Alibaba Cloud. By leveraging the strengths of both CSPs, businesses can achieve optimal performance and scalability while addressing region-specific constraints.

In summary, the rise of multi-cloud strategies is driven by the need to reduce vendor lock-in, comply with regional regulations, optimize global performance, and enhance flexibility in workload distribution. These factors are central to the AWS-Alibaba Cloud integration explored in this thesis, which aims to provide a strategic framework for overcoming the challenges and maximizing the benefits of multi-cloud deployments.

2.2 Distinguishing Multi-Cloud from Related Concepts

Although multi-cloud computing is increasingly prevalent, the terminology surrounding it remains inconsistent. Hong et al. [6] attempt to clarify this by defining four

related models: multi-cloud, hybrid cloud, federated cloud, and cross-cloud computing. Their definitions are based on a synthesis of existing literature:

1. **Multi-Cloud:** The use of multiple cloud providers for distinct services or workloads, often to avoid vendor lock-in or leverage specific provider strengths.
2. **Hybrid Cloud:** A combination of private and public cloud environments, integrated to support workload portability and data exchange.
3. **Federated Cloud Computing:** A cooperative framework among independent cloud providers to enable interoperability and shared resource access.
4. **Cross-Cloud Computing:** Systems designed to support service interaction across cloud boundaries, typically through abstraction or orchestration layers.

Deb et al. [29] stress that hybrid cloud strategies require technical integration and orchestration mechanisms to enable seamless service delivery. Seth et al. [30], meanwhile, emphasize that multi-cloud strategies are often adopted for their resilience, flexibility, and ability to align workloads with optimal providers. Their framing highlights how multi-cloud differs from hybrid models, particularly in terms of governance and intent.

This thesis adopts “multi-cloud” as the primary conceptual framework, reflecting the targeted use of AWS and Alibaba Cloud for distinct workload deployment. While aspects of hybrid and cross-cloud computing are also closely related, the approach is best understood through the lens of multi-cloud architecture.

2.3 Challenges in Multi-Cloud Migration

This section explores the complexities of migrating workloads across multiple CSPs.

2.3.1 Interoperability Challenges

Interoperability challenges are probably the most difficult part of multi-cloud migration. Many papers have already explored different tactics to overcome this. Kumar et al. have reviewed many of these approaches in their paper [31]. The main difficulties lie in differences in APIs and Services, but different Identity and Access Management (IAM) policies and networking configurations across CSPs also play a role.

Barhate et al. [32] classify interoperability challenges into five levels, providing a valuable framework for understanding the multifaceted nature of the problem:

- **Agreement Level:** This includes contractual and protocol-level agreements, distinguishing between syntactic interoperability, where systems can communicate using defined data formats and APIs, and semantic interoperability, which requires accurate contextual understanding of exchanged data.
- **Adoption Level:** Interoperability is also influenced by whether systems adopt standard technologies. This level distinguishes between interoperability by

design, when systems are built with shared standards, and post-facto interoperability, which occurs after systems retroactively conform to widely adopted practices.

- **Deployment Level:** Cloud service models (IaaS, PaaS, SaaS) further complicate interoperability. Horizontal interoperability focuses on integration within the same layer (e.g., AWS Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2) to Alibaba Cloud Elastic Compute Service (ECS)), whereas vertical interoperability involves bridging across layers (e.g., an AWS Lambda function interacting with an Alibaba Cloud database service).
- **Interaction Patterns:** Synchronous interoperability (e.g., real-time services) and asynchronous interoperability (e.g., message queues, batch processes) demand different architectural designs, especially in latency-sensitive applications.
- **End-User Level:** This includes both provider-level interoperability (using standards like The Cloud Data Management Interface (CDMI) or Open Virtualization Format (OVF)) and user-centric interoperability (ensuring users experience seamless service regardless of the cloud provider).

When applying this classification to AWS and Alibaba Cloud, interoperability issues manifest in several concrete forms. For example differences in IAM models complicate user role mapping and access control. API discrepancies require either translation layers or abstraction frameworks. Variations in networking configurations, such as VPC structure and peering models, demand custom routing and firewall rules. Divergent security postures and compliance certifications (e.g., FedRAMP vs. MLPS) can limit mutual operability in regulated industries.

Together, these factors demonstrate that successful multi-cloud adoption requires technical translation, architectural foresight and sometimes organizational policy alignment. In the subsequent chapters, it will be explored how these interoperability challenges were addressed in a real-world AWS-Alibaba Cloud deployment.

2.3.2 Security and Compliance Challenges

Security and compliance are critical concerns when deploying workloads across multiple cloud providers, particularly in regions with distinct regulatory landscapes. A major challenge arises from cross-border compliance requirements, such as data sovereignty laws that dictate where data must reside. For example, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union and China's Cybersecurity Law impose stringent restrictions on data movement, processing, and storage [4]. In this context the Cyberspace Administration of China details many of these regulations in a Q&A. For example it outlines how "general" data is allowed to flow freely across borders and "important" data has to pass a formal security assessment first and how to identify which data is considered which [33]. Regional frameworks often conflict, making it difficult to design a unified, compliant solution in a multi-cloud setup.

Beyond compliance, security policies must also be managed across heterogeneous

environments. AWS and Alibaba Cloud implement different encryption mechanisms, IAM policies, and logging standards, which complicates consistent policy enforcement [34]–[36]. While AWS uses services like AWS Key Management Service (KMS) for encryption and AWS Identity and Access Management (IAM) for access control, Alibaba Cloud relies on its own equivalents, such as Alibaba Cloud Key Management Service (KMS) and Alibaba Cloud Resource Access Management (RAM) [37], [38]. These differences make it harder to implement a unified zero-trust security model and often require custom configuration and policy translation layers to align identity, authentication, and auditing mechanisms across CSPs [25].

Additionally, certification standards (e.g., ISO/IEC 27001, FedRAMP) can vary across cloud providers [39]. Ensuring continuous compliance across CSPs introduces administrative overhead and technical challenges in logging, reporting, and incident response alignment. This makes security and compliance not just a configuration task but a strategic design problem in multi-cloud architectures.

Security is also becoming more important because of the increasing use of AI services. Because of the high reliance on underlying cloud data, attacks can significantly impair those applications [40].

2.3.3 Performance and Cost Optimization Challenges

Multi-cloud deployments introduce performance and cost trade-offs that are difficult to optimize uniformly. One of the most pressing concerns is network latency caused by geographical dispersion and cross-cloud communication overhead [22]. Applications that require low-latency interaction, such as real-time analytics or IoT platforms, can suffer significant performance degradation when components are spread across different CSPs and regions.

Another cost-related challenge is bandwidth pricing, which can vary significantly between providers and regions. For instance, data egress fees from AWS to the public Internet or another cloud can be substantially higher than internal transfers, making frequent data movement between AWS and Alibaba Cloud potentially expensive [28].

Workload distribution must also consider compute performance, storage I/O operations per second limits, and scaling behaviors, which differ across cloud platforms. While one provider may offer better GPU-based instances for machine learning tasks, another may be more cost-effective for storage-heavy workloads. Choosing the optimal platform for each workload component requires continuous performance benchmarking and cost modeling [15], [41].

2.4 Best Practices in Cloud Infrastructure Portability

This section presents techniques to enhance portability and mitigate the challenges discussed above.

2.4.1 Use of Abstraction Layers and Middleware

A popular approach to ensure portability is the use of abstraction layers [42]. A few of the currently most common solutions are the following:

- **Containerization:** Containerized applications can be deployed on almost any cloud infrastructure. There is also Kubernetes, which serves as a tool in standardizing deployments across multiple CSPs. By orchestrating containers, Kubernetes ensures consistent deployment and management, facilitating workload portability and reducing vendor lock-in. The standard it defines for the deployment and management of container images is crucial in achieving the best portability [43].
- **Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC) with Terraform:** Tools like Terraform enable the automation of cloud provisioning through declarative configuration files. By codifying infrastructure, it allows for version control, repeatable deployments, and consistent environments across various CSPs. This approach streamlines the provisioning process and also promotes infrastructure standardization in complex cloud landscapes [44].
- **Cloud Management Platforms (CMPs):** CMPs are similar to IaC but usually go a step further and provide a complete unified interface for managing resources across diverse cloud environments. They offer centralized control, monitoring, and automation capabilities, simplifying the complexities inherent in multi-cloud operations [45]. By abstracting the underlying differences among CSPs, CMPs enable organizations to optimize performance and cost-efficiency. However, in their research Xu et al. [45] also conclude that most multi-cloud management platforms are only compatible with a few heterogeneous cloud resources which can lead to poor compatibility and adaptability.

A deeper comparison of Infrastructure as Code and Cloud Development Kits (CDKs), including Terraform/OpenTofu, AWS CDK, Alibaba Cloud ROS CDK, Pulumi, Crossplane, CDKTF, and their implications for AWS-Alibaba Cloud interoperability is presented next.

2.4.2 Infrastructure as Code and Cloud Development Kits

Infrastructure as Code (IaC) and Cloud Development Kits (CDKs) are central to achieving repeatable, testable, and auditable provisioning in multi-cloud settings. This subsection surveys representative tools, compares their trade-offs, and highlights patterns relevant to AWS-Alibaba Cloud interoperability.

Taxonomy: Declarative IaC vs. Programmatic CDKs

IaC tools broadly fall into:

- **Declarative IaC:** The desired end state is described in a domain-specific language and reconciled by an engine (e.g., Terraform/OpenTofu) [46].

- **Programmatic CDKs:** Infrastructure is authored in general-purpose languages and synthesized to a declarative engine or provider APIs (e.g., AWS CDK to CloudFormation; Alibaba ROS CDK to ROS) [47], [48].

Hybrid approaches such as CDK for Terraform (CDKTF) preserve CDK ergonomics while targeting Terraform's multi-cloud engine [46].

Representative Tools

OpenTofu (open source fork of Terraform) Declarative IaC with mature multi-cloud provider ecosystems, explicit state management, plan/apply workflows, and a large module Registry [49].

AWS Cloud Development Kit (AWS CDK) Programmatic modeling of AWS resources with typed constructs (L1—CFN resources; L2—service-oriented; L3—patterns), synthesizing to CloudFormation; excellent for AWS-centric stacks and deep service integrations [47].

Alibaba Cloud ROS CDK Programmatic modeling of Alibaba Cloud resources synthesizing to ROS templates; mirrors the AWS CDK developer experience for Alibaba Cloud services [48].

CDK for Terraform (CDKTF) CDK authoring style targeting Terraform's engine, combining higher-level composition with Terraform's providers, state management, and plan/apply semantics for multi-cloud portability [46].

Pulumi Programmatic IaC with first-class language SDKs and its own engine, supporting multi-cloud and Kubernetes; integrates well with application developer workflows, testing, and packaging [50].

Crossplane Kubernetes-based control plane using CRDs to manage cloud resources declaratively; composes managed resources and pairs naturally with GitOps (Argo CD/Flux) for reconciliation-driven multi-cloud operations [51]–[53].

Comparative Considerations

- **Portability:** Terraform/OpenTofu, Pulumi, and CDKTF are broadly provider-agnostic; AWS CDK and ROS CDK are strongest within their native ecosystems.
- **Execution Engine:** CloudFormation (AWS CDK), ROS (ROS CDK), Terraform/OpenTofu (Terraform/CDKTF), Pulumi's own engine, and Kubernetes reconciliation (Crossplane).
- **Ecosystem:** Terraform Registry/OpenTofu-compatible modules are extensive; AWS Construct Hub and Pulumi Registry offer higher-level components; Crossplane providers and compositions are growing.

- **State and Drift:** Terraform/OpenTofu/CDKTF maintain explicit state; CloudFormation/ROS track stacks; Pulumi uses its backend; Crossplane reconciles desired vs. observed state continuously.
- **Governance:** OPA, Sentinel (Terraform Cloud/Enterprise), organizational rule-sets, and Kubernetes admission controllers enable policy-as-code across tools [51].
- **GitOps Fit:** Crossplane is GitOps-native; others integrate via CI/CD pipelines, with CDKs synthesizing templates before deployment [52], [53].

Open Challenges and Research Gaps

Open challenges remain in (i) coverage parity—provider and module maturity still lag in parts of the ecosystem (e.g., Crossplane providers and higher-level modules)—and (ii) unified governance across heterogeneous engines, including consistent tagging, cost allocation, and compliance controls.

Current research largely focuses on single-tool approaches to multi-cloud, typically Terraform-based (e.g., Kyadasu et al. [44]), or on comparisons between Terraform and provider-native tooling from major CSPs (e.g., Joao et al. [54] comparing Terraform and AWS CDK). This work seeks to bridge that gap by incorporating the Alibaba Cloud perspective and evaluating interoperability across both CSPs with provider-native and provider-agnostic IaC tools.

2.4.3 Security Best Practices

To reduce the risk of security impediments in multi-cloud environments, several best practices should be considered. The research by Nair et al. [34] identifies three core principles:

Adopting a Multi-Tiered Security Strategy

The first principle is to implement a multi-tiered approach, ensuring security across physical facilities, infrastructure, and cloud services [34]. This involves:

- **Data Protection:** Employ conventional methods such as identity and access management (IAM), encryption (at rest and in transit), secure deletion, and data masking. In multi-cloud setups, it is essential to classify data, define usage policies, and manage access according to sensitivity, especially as data may reside in different jurisdictions. Maintaining logical control over data is critical, even when third parties manage physical infrastructure.
- **Network Security:** Multi-cloud architectures require robust network protection, including virtual LANs, Software-Defined Networks (SDNs), and proxy-based encryption. These tools enable traffic segmentation and secure inter-cloud data flows. Organizations should understand their cloud providers' network con-

figurations and enforce security checkpoints, such as intrusion detection and prevention systems (IDS/IPS).

Solutions in Multi-Cloud Setups

Hybrid and multi-cloud environments, which blend on-premises infrastructure with multiple cloud platforms, present unique challenges. Nair et al. [34] emphasize that data security is more critical than perimeter defense in these architectures. Recommended strategies include:

- **Automating Security Processes:** Use third-party tools for monitoring, incident response, and compliance tracking, which are especially useful in complex, multi-cloud deployments.
- **Encrypting Control Plane Communications:** Secure communication channels that manage orchestration across clouds to prevent tampering or interception.
- **Policy Adherence and User Training:** Enforce strict security protocols and provide user training to mitigate risks of insider threats and accidental breaches, which can be more difficult to monitor across multiple clouds.

Zero Trust Architecture

The "zero trust" security model marks a significant shift from traditional network defense. Zero Trust eliminates implicit trust in any user or device, whether internal or external [55], [56]. Key principles include:

- **Continuous Authentication and Authorization:** Validate every session, regardless of location or device.
- **Least Privilege Access:** Ensure users and services have only the access necessary for their role.
- **Micro-segmentation:** Limit lateral movement within the network by segmenting resources.

Moudni et al. [25] highlight that applying Zero Trust in a multi-cloud context is important to ensure security and availability of data. In their paper they propose a zero-trust based access layer to enable, control and end connections between user or service and the desired resource. With this system it doesn't matter where or on which CSP the resources are located and is therefore a viable approach for multi-cloud architectures.

2.4.4 Monitoring and Performance Management

Monitoring and managing performance in multi-cloud environments is essential for ensuring application reliability, user experience, and cost-effectiveness. Compared to single-cloud deployments, multi-cloud architectures introduce greater complexity due

to the heterogeneity of platforms, APIs, and management interfaces. This requires comprehensive observability solutions and advanced optimization techniques to maintain seamless operations across all cloud service providers (CSPs).

A key challenge in multi-cloud monitoring is aggregating and correlating metrics, logs, and traces from multiple sources. Traditional monitoring tools are often designed for single-provider environments and may struggle to interpret provider-specific data or offer a unified view [45]. To address this, organizations often use open-source and vendor-neutral observability tools such as Prometheus and Grafana [57]. Prometheus can collect and store time series data from diverse cloud environments, while Grafana provides flexible dashboards for visualizing and correlating metrics across CSPs. These tools enable real-time monitoring, alerting, and capacity planning in distributed deployments.

Alongside open-source solutions, native offerings from CSPs such as AWS CloudWatch [38] and Alibaba Cloud CloudMonitor [37] provide robust monitoring features within their respective ecosystems. However, integrating these tools in a multi-cloud context often necessitates additional aggregation layers or middleware to centralize and normalize telemetry data [58, pp. 210-216]. This underscores the importance of standardizing observability practices and, where possible, adopting open standards to facilitate consistent monitoring across differing environments.

As multi-cloud environments grow in scale and complexity, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning are increasingly leveraged for performance optimization. AI-driven monitoring platforms can analyze large volumes of data to identify system bottlenecks, forecast demand, and automatically adjust resource allocation in real time [59]. These systems can recommend or enact workload balancing based on latency and cost, and can proactively detect and remediate anomalies or resource conflicts.

Despite these advances, several challenges remain in implementing effective monitoring and performance management across multiple clouds. Amgothu et al. [16] highlight that scattered monitoring data across platforms requiring manual aggregation, latency of monitoring tools from geographically dispersed cloud regions, and tools that may not scale uniformly across clouds may hinder unified observability. In their research they suggest best practices to mitigate these issues which include unification of data collection, establishing proactive monitoring and automating alerting systems.

In summary, monitoring and performance management are foundational to successful multi-cloud strategies. By combining open-source observability tools, AI-driven optimization, and standardized practices, organizations can achieve reliable, efficient, and resilient multi-cloud operations. This is particularly critical in scenarios involving AWS–Alibaba Cloud integration, where differences in monitoring capabilities and APIs make a coordinated and adaptive approach essential.

2.5 Emerging Trends and Research Gaps

As multi-cloud computing matures, new paradigms and technologies are shaping its evolution, while unresolved challenges continue to motivate ongoing research. This section presents a focused overview of recent innovations in multi-cloud environments and highlights research gaps that are particularly relevant to AWS–Alibaba Cloud interoperability.

Innovations in Multi-Cloud

One of the most significant trends in the multi-cloud landscape is the adoption of cloud-native application design, particularly through microservices and serverless computing. Microservice architectures decompose applications into loosely coupled, independently deployable components, enabling organizations to distribute workloads across multiple cloud service providers (CSPs) and achieve greater elasticity and resilience [60], [61]. There are also attempts to facilitate the idea of multi-cloud native applications. In the literature review by Alonso et al. [5] they come to the conclusion that there is no universal understanding of multi-cloud native applications yet but they classify them into three main categories. Those covering replicated applications, those that are fully distributed applications and those that are a combination of both. Specific architectural patterns or design methods specific for multi-cloud still prove to be an important challenge.

Serverless computing further abstracts infrastructure management, allowing developers to write and deploy code that automatically scales in response to demand, making it easier to build portable and cost-effective solutions that span different clouds. Current research is trying to find solutions for the vendor lock-in problems in serverless. Baarzi et al. [62] propose a virtual serverless provider that dynamically chooses the best CSP based on current pricing and performance. Another example would be a common interface in the form of a multi-cloud library to access resources by different clouds. A first version of this was created by Zhao et al. [19].

Artificial intelligence (AI) and automation are also transforming how organizations manage multi-cloud environments. AI-driven orchestration platforms leverage telemetry data to predict workload demands, optimize resource allocation, and automate remediation tasks in real time. These systems can identify performance bottlenecks, recommend optimal workload placements, and ensure cost efficiency across heterogeneous infrastructures [55]. As multi-cloud deployments grow in complexity, such intelligent systems are becoming essential for maintaining reliability and operational efficiency.

Security is another area experiencing rapid innovation, with the zero trust security model gaining traction in multi-cloud settings. Unlike traditional security approaches that rely on network perimeters, zero trust assumes no implicit trust and enforces continuous verification of users, devices, and services regardless of their network location [25], [55], [56]. The adoption of zero trust architectures helps organizations mitigate risks associated with distributed, cross-cloud operations and maintain consistent

security postures across diverse environments.

Research Gaps Relevant to AWS-Alibaba Cloud Integration

Despite these advances, notable research gaps persist, especially regarding the specific integration of AWS and Alibaba Cloud. A primary challenge lies in the lack of standardized frameworks for interoperability between these providers. Differences in API design, resource abstractions, and identity and access management (IAM) models present significant barriers to seamless workload migration and unified management [12]. While general strategies for multi-cloud interoperability have been explored in the literature, there is limited research focused on the unique technical and operational challenges of AWS-Alibaba Cloud environments.

Another important gap concerns compliance and regulatory alignment. AWS and Alibaba Cloud operate under distinct legal and regulatory regimes, particularly in regions such as China and the European Union. Organizations seeking to deploy workloads across both providers must navigate complex data sovereignty, privacy, and security requirements, yet there is a shortage of empirical studies and best practices for addressing these challenges in practice [4], [39].

Finally, there is a need for validated, real-world frameworks and tools that address performance, security, and cost considerations in AWS-Alibaba Cloud environments. Studies to date lack practical evaluations, case studies, or actionable methodologies tailored to the integration of these specific providers. By developing and assessing a strategic framework for AWS-Alibaba Cloud interoperability, this thesis aims to bridge these research gaps and contribute practical guidance for organizations seeking to maximize the benefits of multi-cloud strategies.

In summary, while innovations such as microservices, serverless computing, AI-driven optimization, and zero trust security are advancing the state of multi-cloud computing, significant challenges remain, particularly in the context of integrating AWS and Alibaba Cloud. Addressing these gaps is essential for enabling secure, efficient, and compliant multi-cloud operations in a global context.

Chapter 3

Research Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodological approach for analyzing, designing, and validating a multi-cloud strategy for AWS and Alibaba Cloud interoperability. The methodology is structured to ensure a systematic, reproducible, and practically relevant assessment, and is closely aligned with the research objectives introduced in Chapter 1 and the literature context provided in Chapter 2.

3.1 Methodological Approach

The research adopts a comparative and exploratory methodology that combines literature review, structured comparative analysis, and a proof-of-concept (PoC) implementation. This approach was chosen to address both theoretical and practical aspects of multi-cloud strategy, and to fill the research gap identified in Chapter 1 regarding real-world AWS-Alibaba Cloud integration.

- **Comparative Analysis:** Key differences and similarities between AWS and Alibaba Cloud are systematically identified, focusing on infrastructure, services, APIs, security, and compliance.
- **Exploratory Research:** Multiple deployment and migration strategies are considered, with a focus on practical approaches relevant to enterprise workloads.
- **Proof-of-Concept:** A representative workload is implemented and migrated using selected infrastructure-as-code (IaC) tools to empirically validate the comparative findings.

3.2 Comparative Analysis Framework

To enable a transparent and actionable evaluation, the following domains are used as the comparative framework. These categories and metrics draw from existing studies ([41], [63], [64]) and practical needs for multi-cloud workload migration:

Figure 3.1: Comparative Analysis Framework for AWS and Alibaba Cloud. Each domain is an important part of the evaluation.

1. **Global Infrastructure & Reach:** Distribution of data centers and regional presence
2. **Messaging & API Gateway:** Managed messaging, event buses, and API options
3. **Compute:** VM, serverless, and container service offerings
4. **Database & Storage:** Database, Object, and file storage service offerings
5. **Analytics:** Data lakes, analytics services, and big data processing
6. **Networking:** Virtual Private Cloud (VPC), Domain Name System (DNS), and Content Delivery Network (CDN) service offerings
7. **Security & Identity:** Identity Management, Firewall
8. **IoT & Edge:** Managed IoT platforms and edge computing
9. **Compliance:** Regulatory alignments
10. **Infrastructure as Code & Automation:** Maturity and portability of IaC tools (e.g., AWS CDK, ROS CDK, Terraform)

11. **Operational Complexity:** Usability, support, documentation, and third-party integrations

This framework forms the backbone of the comparative analysis in chapter 4 and informs both the strategy development and the proof-of-concept implementation.

3.3 Multi-Cloud Strategy Development

The development process, detailed in chapter 5, builds upon the comparative analysis of AWS and Alibaba Cloud presented in chapter 4. The goal is to design a robust multi-cloud integration strategy that addresses the architectural, operational, and compliance challenges identified earlier in the thesis.

The development of the multi-cloud strategy follows these steps:

1. **Synthesis of Comparative Findings:** Key differences and similarities in infrastructure, service portfolios, APIs, and security models (as analyzed in chapter 4) are synthesized to identify integration strengths, weaknesses, threats, and opportunities.
2. **Selection of Reference Architectures:** Drawing on literature and industry practice, suitable architectural patterns (e.g., serverless, container-based, or hybrid) are reviewed and mapped to the interoperability requirements of AWS and Alibaba Cloud in typical use-cases.
3. **Evaluation of Infrastructure as Code Tooling:** The suitability of provider-native (AWS CDK, Alibaba ROS CDK) and agnostic (Terraform/OpenTofu) IaC tools is assessed, with the aim of balancing feature completeness, maintainability, and portability.
4. **Design Principles and Best Practices:** The strategy incorporates best practices for security, compliance, identity management, and monitoring, as identified in both literature (see chapter 3) and the comparative analysis.
5. **Decision Rationale:** Where multiple viable solutions exist (e.g., native vs. agnostic IaC, managed vs. containerized services), trade-offs are explicitly documented and justified based on empirical findings and project objectives.
6. **Architecture Blueprint:** A key result artifact of the multi-cloud strategy is formalized as a reference architecture and deployment workflow, providing clear implementation guidelines for the proof-of-concept in chapter 6.

This process ensures that the proposed multi-cloud strategy is not only theoretically grounded but also practically validated against the specific challenges of AWS-Alibaba Cloud integration. The outputs of this strategy development directly inform the implementation and evaluation phases of the thesis.

3.4 Deployment Steps

The following sequential steps operationalize the above strategy and provide the empirical basis for evaluation:

1. **Reference Workload Definition:** Specify a representative multi-cloud workload that exercises compute, storage, networking, and at least one advanced managed service (e.g., IoT or messaging), as outlined in chapter 5.
2. **AWS Native Deployment (AWS CDK):** Implement and deploy the workload using AWS CDK. All required resources, configurations, and deployment steps are documented.
3. **Alibaba Cloud Native Deployment (ROS CDK):** Translate the AWS CDK definitions into Alibaba ROS CDK, adapting for service and API differences, and deploy on Alibaba Cloud. All necessary changes and challenges are recorded.
4. **Cross-Platform IaC Deployment (Terraform/OpenTofu):** Define the same workload in a provider-agnostic way using Terraform/OpenTofu, and attempt deployment to both AWS and Alibaba Cloud. Limitations and differences relative to native IaC toolchains are documented.
5. **Service Gap Analysis:** For each deployment, evaluate whether all required managed services are functionally available and equivalent. If a critical gap is found, analytically outline how a container or VM solution could be deployed to address the limitation.
6. **Documentation and Data Collection:** Throughout the process, systematically collect code, configurations, deployment outputs, and all observations necessary for evaluation.

3.5 Evaluation Methodology

Each deployment and migration approach is evaluated using both quantitative and qualitative criteria that reflect real-world multi-cloud needs:

- **Portability:** How easily can the workload and infrastructure definitions be migrated between AWS and Alibaba Cloud?
- **Expressiveness:** Can the required features and services be fully represented in the chosen IaC and CSP toolchains?
- **Deployment Effort:** How complex and time-consuming is the deployment and adaptation process?
- **Operational Complexity:** What are the ongoing management, update, and troubleshooting requirements for each approach?
- **Service Compatibility:** Are there critical gaps or incompatibilities in managed services, and how are they addressed?

- **Cost and Performance (where measurable):** Where possible, collect indicative cost and performance data for each deployment.

All findings are recorded systematically, with special attention to points of friction, required workarounds, and the trade-offs between native and cross-platform IaC tools. If containers or virtual machines are considered, their expected impact is discussed.

3.6 Summary

This methodology ensures both a rigorous comparative analysis and a practical, hands-on validation of multi-cloud migration strategies between AWS and Alibaba Cloud. The next chapter applies this methodology to a detailed comparative analysis, laying the groundwork for developing and evaluating a concrete multi-cloud strategy.

Chapter 4

AWS vs. Alibaba Cloud: A Comparative Analysis

This chapter delivers a side-by-side comparison of AWS and Alibaba Cloud, covering global infrastructure, core services, APIs and automation, security and identity, and regulatory concerns. Each section highlights the key distinctions and trade-offs for educated multi-cloud architecture decisions. The chapter's structure is analogous to the Comparative Analysis Framework introduced in section 3.2, while service-specific content is consolidated in section 4.2.

4.1 Global Infrastructure & Reach

A provider's global footprint underpins latency, availability, resilience, and data-residency guarantees in any multi-cloud deployment. In this section, Amazon Web Services (AWS) and Alibaba Cloud are compared along four dimensions:

1. *Region and availability zone count*: The number and distribution of geographic regions and availability zones (AZs).
2. *Specialized partitions*: Isolated environments for government or restricted-data workloads.
3. *Data-residency controls*: Native mechanisms to enforce where data may be stored or processed.
4. *Network reach*: The extent of inter-region backbones and edge presence.

As of mid-2025, AWS operates 36 regions and 114 AZs worldwide, with especially deep coverage in North America and Europe. Alibaba Cloud, with 29 regions and 87 AZs, excels in Greater China and Southeast Asia while steadily expanding its global backbone [65], [66]. Both platforms provide specialized partitions, namely AWS GovCloud and AWS China, Alibaba China Mainland and Alibaba GovCloud to satisfy strict regulatory requirements. Table 4.2 offers a short overview on this. Data-residency controls are how a provider keeps your data within a chosen jurisdiction. AWS

emphasizes granular in-country placement (Regions/AZs plus Local Zones/Outposts) with org-wide Service Control Policy (SCP) guardrails to block cross-region movement. Alibaba Cloud emphasizes strict Region/partition separation (Mainland China vs. International) enforced via RAM/Resource Directory policies; cross-region features are opt-in. Also keep in mind that the way edge locations are counted, might vary between the CSPs.

Characteristic	AWS	Alibaba Cloud
Regions	36	29
Availability Zones	114	87
Strongest Presence	North America, Europe	China, Southeast Asia
Specialized Partitions	AWS GovCloud, AWS China	China Mainland, Outside Mainland
Data-Residency Controls	Local Zones and policy control	Region selection and policy control
Global Edge Locations (criteria might vary)	400+	3200+

Table 4.2: Comparison of AWS and Alibaba Cloud Global Infrastructure [65], [66]

Key takeaway: AWS's broader geographic reach enables lower latency failover and more fine-grained disaster recovery zones, whereas Alibaba Cloud's deep connection to China and Southeast Asia may provide and performance advantages in those markets.

4.2 Core Service Portfolio

A multi-cloud strategy hinges on understanding each provider's managed services. This section maps AWS and Alibaba Cloud offerings across seven categories: Messaging & API Gateway, Compute, Database & Storage, Analytics, Networking, Security & Identity, and IoT & Edge, highlighting both direct equivalents and notable feature differences. Figure 4.1 provides an overview and rates the functional equivalence of Alibaba services to their AWS counterparts using Harvey Balls; these ratings are informed by the analysis that follows. Prior comparisons that include Alibaba Cloud's own [67], [68] exist. This analysis aims to close gaps in those works, particularly where close equivalents are lacking or previously cited services are deprecated (e.g., certain IoT services). The primary sources are the current official service documentations.

Messaging & API Gateway

AWS Simple Queue Service (SQS) provides durable, at-least-once queuing (Standard queue) or exactly-once message processing and high-throughput mode (FIFO queue). It offers features including dead-letter queues, supports short or long polling, and up to 14-day retention. AWS Simple Notification Service (SNS) offers pub/sub delivery to

Figure 4.1: Service comparison between AWS and Alibaba Cloud core service portfolio [37], [38], [67]

SQS, Lambda, HTTP, Email, Mobile device, SMS, Data Firehose, and different service providers (e.g., MongoDB). [69], [70]

Alibaba Simple Message Queue (SMQ) combines queue-based or topic-based messaging with dead-letter queues, short or long polling, and up to 7-day retention. Both SMQ-modes don't support FIFO queue and topic-based SMQ supports pub/sub delivery to SMQ, FC, HTTP, Email, SMS, and Mobile device. [71]

Both AWS API Gateway and Alibaba API Gateway are fully managed services that let you create, secure, and monitor high-performance APIs for connecting clients to backend services at scale. [72], [73]

Compute

Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2) and Alibaba Cloud Elastic Cloud Service (ECS) offer different instance types that are optimized depending on use case (e.g., General, Compute, Memory, Storage). [74], [75]

AWS Lambda and Alibaba Cloud Function Compute both provide on-demand, event-driven "serverless" compute platforms with automatic scaling and pay-per-use billing. [76], [77]

AWS Elastic Kubernetes Service (EKS) and Alibaba Cloud Container Service for Kubernetes (ACK) are both fully managed Kubernetes control planes that abstract away master-node operations, ensure high availability. [78], [79]

Database & Storage

AWS Relational Database Service (RDS) and Alibaba Cloud ApsaraDB RDS can manage relational databases that are queried with SQL. [80], [81]

DynamoDB is a managed, serverless NoSQL database. Table Store delivers comparable features but has no true on-demand capacity mode, as it bills per Compute Unit (CU) instead of per request. [82], [83]

AWS S3 and Alibaba Object Storage Service (OSS) are fully managed object-storage solutions, each supporting diverse storage classes to meet a range of performance and retention needs. AWS S3 offers S3 Standard, S3 Intelligent-Tiering, S3 Standard-Infrequent Access (Standard-IA), S3 One Zone-Infrequent Access (One Zone-IA), S3 Express One Zone, S3 Glacier Instant Retrieval, S3 Glacier Flexible Retrieval, and S3 Glacier Deep Archive. In contrast, Alibaba OSS provides Standard, Infrequent Access (IA), Archive, Cold Archive, and Deep Cold Archive storage classes. S3 leads in the number and granularity of storage class options. [84], [85]

Analytics

AWS Athena is a serverless service that lets users run SQL queries directly on data stored in S3, enabling fast, ad-hoc analytics with no setup. In contrast, Alibaba Cloud

AnalyticDB supports SQL for both real-time and batch processing on internal data or data in OSS, but requires cluster configuration. Thus, Athena is simpler and quicker to use, while AnalyticDB offers more complex features and optimization for larger workloads. [86], [87]

AWS EMR and Alibaba E-MapReduce both run managed Hadoop and Spark clusters for big data processing in the cloud. [88], [89]

AWS Kinesis Data Firehose and Alibaba Cloud Simple Log Service (SLS) both handle real-time data ingestion, transformation, and delivery to their cloud platforms. A key difference is that Firehose focuses on streaming data delivery, while SLS also includes built-in log analytics and monitoring features. [90], [91]

Networking

AWS CloudFront and Alibaba Cloud Content Delivery Network (CDN) are global content delivery network services that speed up web content delivery by caching data at edge locations. Both reduce latency and improve performance. [92], [93]

AWS Route 53 and Alibaba Cloud Domain Name System (DNS) both offer reliable, scalable DNS management with global coverage. [94], [95]

AWS VPC and Alibaba Cloud VPC both let you create secure, isolated virtual networks in the cloud. [96], [97]

Security & Identity

AWS Cognito and Alibaba Cloud IDaaS both provide cloud-based user authentication and access management, integrating with their respective cloud services. [98], [99]

AWS Identity and Access Management (IAM) and Alibaba Cloud Resource Access Management (RAM) offer the same core features access management, including user, group, and role management, as well as permission controls. This will be explored further in 4.4. [100], [101]

AWS Web Application Firewall (WAF) and Alibaba Cloud WAF both protect web apps from threats like SQL injection and XSS, offering customizable rules and real-time monitoring. [102], [103]

IoT

AWS IoT Core supports secure device connectivity, flexible protocols, and seamless integration with other AWS services. Alibaba Cloud ApsaraMQ for MQTT provides scalable MQTT messaging but lacks advanced device management and integration features found in IoT Core. [104], [105]

AWS Greengrass offers edge computing for IoT, enabling local compute and sync when offline. Alibaba Cloud has **no** direct equivalent service to Greengrass! [106]

AWS IoT Analytics delivers managed pipelines for processing IoT data, while Alibaba Cloud lacks a truly equivalent service. Simple Log Service (SLS) can be used for basic data ingestion and analytics. [91], [107]

Central Sources and Clarifications

The foundational references for this service comparison are the official and prior comparative documents [37], [38], [67], [68], which provide broad overviews of AWS and Alibaba Cloud service portfolios. However, this analysis highlights gaps and updates not clearly addressed or out-of-date in those sources, including:

- Alibaba Cloud currently **does not provide a direct equivalent to AWS Green-grass**, which offers edge computing capabilities for IoT devices [106].
- The Alibaba IoT platform service previously noted in prior comparisons has since been **deprecated** and is supposed to be replaced by the much less capable ApsaraMQ for MQTT as noted before.
- Several Alibaba managed services differ in feature sets and operational modes compared to AWS (e.g., no FIFO support in Alibaba Simple Message Queue).
- This updated review is based on the latest official documentation releases through 2025 to reflect current capabilities not accounted for in earlier comparisons.

Implications for Multi-Cloud:

- **Service Equivalency is Not Uniform:** Directly analogous services across AWS and Alibaba Cloud often differ in performance, configuration options, and operational limits. Architects must validate equivalency in features, Service Level Agreements (SLA), and scaling behavior before treating services as interchangeable.
- **Performance and Cost Divergence:** Nominally identical instance types or storage classes may yield different latency, bandwidth, and pricing profiles, especially under load. Real-world benchmarking and ongoing cost analysis are required to optimize deployments and avoid costly surprises.
- **Resilience and Redundancy Planning:** Variations in service reliability, regional coverage, and feature release cadence mean that failover strategies should be cloud-aware. Critical paths must account for differences in SLA guarantees, API stability, and disaster recovery mechanisms.
- **Operational Complexity Increases:** Managing security, identity, networking, and compliance across clouds introduces policy drift and tooling overhead. If possible, teams should invest in unified monitoring, automated policy enforcement, and cross-cloud identity management to minimize friction and risk.
- **Feature Evolution and Lock-in Risk:** Each provider's innovation rate and roadmap shape the long-term viability of multi-cloud architectures. Regularly

reviewing service updates and deprecation notices helps avoid technical debt and provider lock-in.

4.3 APIs & Automation

Cloud provider APIs and automation frameworks are the linchpins of any multi-cloud deployment. In this section, AWS and Alibaba Cloud are across two dimensions:

1. *API models*: Endpoint topology, authentication/signing, and discoverability.
2. *Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC) tooling*: Native CDKs, declarative templates, and Terraform support.

4.3.1 API Models and Differences

Both AWS and Alibaba Cloud expose RESTful interfaces for nearly every service, but differences in endpoint design, signing mechanisms, and rate-limit governance means that they cannot be mapped one to one. In many cases, Alibaba Cloud will be very similar to AWS. An example of this can be seen in figure 4.2 for the API request to list versions of objects in a Bucket or OSS.

AWS sample request for ListObjectVersions

```
GET /?versions HTTP/1.1
Host: BucketName.s3.<Region>.amazonaws.com
Date: Wed, 28 Oct 2009 22:32:00 +0000
Authorization: authorization string (see Authenticating Requests (AWS Signature Version 4))
```

Alibaba Cloud request structure for ListObjectVersions

```
GET /?versions HTTP/1.1
Host: BucketName.oss-cn-hangzhou.aliyuncs.com
Date: GMT Date
Authorization: SignatureValue
```

Figure 4.2: API request examples [108], [109]

Table 4.4 offers a quick comparison of relevant API characteristics.

Key observations:

- AWS's consistent SigV4 signing and predictable regional endpoints simplify tooling reuse across services; Alibaba's mix of HMAC versions can require manual intervention to stay consistent, but the old version is soon to be deprecated and fully replaced [109].

Characteristic	AWS	Alibaba Cloud
Signing Scheme	AWS Signature Version 4 (HMAC-SHA256) [108]	HMAC-SHA1 (legacy) and Signature Version 4 (HMAC-SHA256) [109]
SDK Coverage	SDKs in 13 languages [110]	SDKs in 6 languages [111]
Discovery	Machine-readable service models with centralized API reference	OpenAPI Portal with per-product API definitions [112]

Table 4.4: Comparison of Core API Models

- SDK behavior is broadly comparable, but minor naming and pagination differences warrant wrappers or adapters in shared libraries.

4.3.2 Infrastructure-as-Code Tooling

IaC frameworks can abstract low-level API calls into higher-order constructs. This subsection compares native CDK offerings, declarative templates, and Terraform support. It considers ease of use, integration depth, extensibility, and suitability for multi-cloud environments. The services that are compared are the AWS Cloud Development Kit (AWS CDK), Alibaba Cloud Resource Orchestration Service Cloud Development Kit (Alibaba Cloud ROS CDK) and Terraform Cloud Development Kit (Terraform CDK). Table 4.6 offers an overview of these tools.

Tool	AWS CDK	Alibaba Cloud ROS CDK	Terraform CDK
Description	Native IaC SDK	Native IaC SDK	Open-source, supports multiple clouds via providers
Languages	TypeScript, Python, Java, C#, Go	TypeScript, Python, Java, C#, Go	TypeScript, Python, Java, C#, Go
Underlying	AWS CloudFormation (YAML/JSON)	Alibaba ROS (YAML/JSON)	Terraform (HCL)
Extensibility	Medium (Third-Party Extensions)	None	High (community modules)
Multi-Cloud	No	No	Yes
Integration	Deep AWS integration	Deep Alibaba integration	Integrates with both
Use Case	AWS-centric automation	Alibaba-centric automation	Multi-cloud/hybrid environments

Table 4.6: IaC Tools Comparison: AWS CDK, Alibaba Cloud ROS CDK, and Terraform CDK [46]–[48]

Discussion:

- CloudFormation and ROS templates serve the same declarative purpose but differ in available resource types and intrinsic functions.
- AWS CDK typically leads in adopting high-level service constructs to ease deployment in fewer lines of code (e.g., L3 constructs [113]).
- Terraform provides a more unified abstraction for both, but provider-specific quirks demand per-cloud module variants [114].
- Drift detection and change-set workflows are similar in concept but differ in CLI UX and error reporting (AWS CDK and ROS CDK have drift detection per CLI and per Cloudformation / ROS, Terraform only per CLI; resources that support drift detection might differ).

4.4 General Security & Identity

A robust security and identity foundation is essential for enforcing consistent policies, managing cryptographic controls, and detecting threats across multiple clouds. We compare AWS and Alibaba Cloud across three areas: (i) compliance certifications, (ii) identity and access management (IAM) models, and (iii) security services and tooling.

Compliance Certifications

Both providers maintain broad compliance portfolios, with regional emphasis reflecting their market presence. Table 4.8 lists commonly referenced frameworks. Availability and scope are service- and region-dependent [115], [116]. Always verify the applicable attestation report or certificate for the specific services and regions in scope.

Certification/Framework	AWS	Alibaba Cloud
ISO/IEC 27001	Yes	Yes
ISO/IEC 27017/27018	Yes	Yes
SOC 1/2/3	Yes	Yes
PCI DSS	Yes	Yes
HIPAA	Yes	Yes
FedRAMP	Yes (incl. GovCloud)	No
EU Cloud Code/BSI C5/ENS	Yes	Yes
China MLPS	Yes (AWS China only)	Yes

Table 4.8: Selected compliance certifications and frameworks (scope can vary by service or region) [115], [116]

Note: GDPR is a regulatory regime rather than a certification; both providers offer Data Processing Addendums and tooling to support controller or processor obligations, but compliance remains a shared responsibility [117], [118].

Identity and Access Management

AWS IAM (Identity and Access Management) and Alibaba Cloud RAM (Resource Access Management) expose broadly similar constructs, namely principals, roles, policies, and temporary credentials, but with differences in syntax, feature depth, and organization-wide guardrails.

Discussion (based on Documentation [100], [101]):

- **Policy language and ABAC:** Both use JSON-based policies and support resource- and condition-based controls. AWS exposes a wider catalog of condition keys and mature tag-based attribute-based access control (ABAC) patterns across more services. Alibaba RAM supports condition keys and tag constraints, but service coverage and condition granularity can differ; confirm per-service authorization model.
- **Roles, federation, and sessions:** Both support role assumption with Security Token Service (STS), Security Assertion Markup Language (SAML)/OpenID Connect (OIDC) federation, and session-limited credentials. AWS integrates with IAM Identity Center (formerly AWS Single-Sign-On (SSO)) and Cognito for application-facing identity; Alibaba provides CloudSSO and Identity Provider (IdP) connectors. Default session durations, token formats, and audience or claim mapping differ and require provider-specific configuration.
- **Permission boundaries and session policies:** AWS supports permission boundaries and session policies consistently across many services. Alibaba offers similar constraints via RAM policies attached to roles and users; review the exact evaluation order and inheritance semantics per product.
- **Organization-level controls:** AWS Organizations provides Service Control Policies (SCPs), Tag Policies, and delegated administration across organizational units [119]. Alibaba Resource Directory offers Control Policies and Tag Policies with hierarchical enforcement across folders and member accounts [120]. Coverage and enforcement semantics vary by service; test critical deny or allow scenarios in both environments.

Security Services and Tooling

Each cloud provides managed defenses, posture management, and detection services. Table 4.10 summarizes core offerings relevant to multi-cloud baselines.

Category	AWS	Alibaba Cloud
DDoS & Edge Protection	AWS Shield Standard-/Advanced; AWS WAF; CloudFront	Anti-DDoS (Basic/Pro/Premium); Web Application Firewall; CDN
Posture & Compliance	AWS Config; Security Hub; Audit Manager	Cloud Config; Security Center (baseline checks); Compliance Center
Threat Detection & Investigation	GuardDuty; Detective; Security Lake	Security Center (threat detection)
Host or Container Security	Amazon Inspector; ECR image scanning; GuardDuty for EKS or ECS	Security Center (host or container); Container Registry security scanning
Logging & Audit	CloudTrail; CloudWatch Logs; CloudTrail Lake	ActionTrail; Simple Log Service (SLS)
Key & Secret Management	AWS KMS (symmetric or asymmetric; HSM; multi-Region keys); Secrets Manager	KMS (symmetric or asymmetric; HSM or dedicated options); Secrets management (KMS or Secrets services)
Network Segmentation	VPC, Security Groups, Network Firewall, PrivateLink	VPC, Security Groups, Cloud Firewall, PrivateLink

Table 4.10: Representative security services [67]

4.5 Regulatory & Data Sovereignty

Regulatory regimes and data-sovereignty requirements impose constraints on where and how workloads operate. The following are examined: (i) China-specific regulations, (ii) regional privacy frameworks, and (iii) cross-border data transfer strategies.

4.5.1 China-Specific Regulatory Environment

Mainland China enforces network controls (commonly referred to as the Great Firewall) and applies the Multi-Level Protection Scheme (MLPS) governing information system security levels, alongside the Cybersecurity Law (CSL), Data Security Law (DSL), and Personal Information Protection Law (PIPL) [121].

- **Operational model and network isolation:** AWS China regions are operated

by licensed local partners (Sinnnet in Beijing; NWCD in Ningxia), with separate accounts, consoles, and endpoints; architectures should treat these as distinct partitions. Alibaba Cloud operates natively within the domestic backbone and offers extensive mainland region coverage [66], [122].

- **MLPS compliance:** Alibaba Cloud public cloud services typically hold MLPS Level 3 certifications (scope varies by service) [116]. AWS parity is available only within AWS China regions operated by local partners [123]. Customer systems may still require filing/assessment depending on industry and level.
- **Data localization and transfers:** CSL, DSL, or PIPL impose onshore storage for critical data and personal information collected in mainland China, with security assessments for cross-border transfers [33], [121]. Expect approval, contractual mechanisms, and technical safeguards before egress.
- **Content delivery considerations:** Serving content within mainland China generally requires ICP filing or licensing [124]; CDN acceleration across the border must respect regulatory constraints.

4.5.2 Regional Privacy Frameworks

Major jurisdictions impose distinct privacy and security obligations; cloud providers offer artifacts and controls to support compliance within a shared responsibility model.

Discussion of a few regional privacy frameworks [116], [123]:

- **GDPR (EU and EEA):** Both providers offer EU regions, Data Processing Addendums (DPA), Standard Contractual Clauses (SCC) mechanisms, and tooling for Data Subject Access Requests. AWS supports region controls and Service Control Policy-based (SPA-based) restrictions; Alibaba offers contractual controls and region or bucket constraints. Record of Processing Activities (RoPA) and transfer impact assessments remain customer obligations.
- **FedRAMP (US Government):** AWS GovCloud (US) provides FedRAMP High or Moderate authorizations for many services; additional services are available on commercial partitions with FedRAMP authorizations. Alibaba does not currently offer a FedRAMP-authorized environment.
- **Other frameworks:** ISO or IEC 27018 (cloud privacy), HITRUST, IRAP (AU), BSI C5 (DE), ENS (ES), and national banking or financial regulations are supported to varying degrees by both.

4.6 Key Trade-offs

To conclude this comparative analysis, Table 4.12 distills the most important differences and distinctions between AWS and Alibaba Cloud. Following, the primary trade-offs that practitioners must reconcile when architecting a multi-cloud environment are outlined.

Aspect	AWS	Alibaba Cloud
Footprint & Reach	Broad global coverage; consistent experience across commercial regions	Strong in Mainland China and SEA; Mainland vs. International separation
Core Service Parity	Mature primitives (compute, object storage, etc.)	Equivalents mostly exist; validate per service
API & SDK	SigV4; regional endpoints; consistent SDK conventions	Per-product endpoints; moving to HMAC-SHA256; similar SDK
IaC & Tooling	CloudFormation/AWS CDK; Terraform provider	ROS/ROS CDK; Terraform provider
Networking & Edge	Global CDN/DNS; private connectivity	Strong CDN/DNS in China; cross-border constraints
Security & Identity	IAM + Organizations	RAM + Resource Directory
Compliance & Sovereignty	FedRAMP; broad attestations; China via separate partitions	MLPS; broad attestations; no FedRAMP

Table 4.12: Condensed comparison of AWS vs. Alibaba Cloud

Trade-offs for Multi-Cloud Strategy

- **Reach vs. Compliance Domains:** AWS's extensive global footprint can lower latency and improve failover, but Alibaba's domestic integration and MLPS support simplify China-focused deployments.
- **Native IaC Depth vs. Uniform Abstraction:** Provider-specific CDKs grant immediate access to new services, whereas cross-cloud tools (Terraform, CDKTF) centralize definitions at the cost of possible provider lag and reduced feature coverage.
- **Policy Language Coherence:** AWS IAM + SCPs and Alibaba RAM + Resource Directory differ in syntax, inheritance, and condition operators, requiring careful policy management.
- **Operational Overhead vs. Vendor Optimization:** Maintaining parallel stacks increases complexity and cost, yet direct use of native services often yields the best performance, Service Level Agreements, and feature velocity.

By weighing these trade-offs, architects can craft a multi-cloud blueprint that balances global performance, regulatory compliance, and operational efficiency. Chapter 5 will build upon these insights to propose concrete design patterns and automation workflows.

Chapter 5

Design of the Multi-Cloud Strategy

This chapter translates the comparative evidence (chapter 4) and the methodological commitments (chapter 3) into a concrete, defensible multi-cloud strategy for AWS and Alibaba Cloud. It defines the target state, clarifies design principles and decision criteria, and specifies the reference architecture implemented and validated in the proof-of-concept (PoC) in chapter 6. The strategy anchors on a serverless-first posture with pragmatic fallbacks to containers and managed VMs where parity or performance requirements dictate. It emphasizes portability, resilience, and regulatory alignment, while acknowledging and mitigating service disparity, operational overhead, and data-sovereignty constraints.

5.1 Scope, Goals, and Design Drivers

This section scopes the problem space, makes explicit assumptions, and states the quality attributes the strategy optimizes for. These drivers frame all later architectural choices and the PoC validation.

Problem Scope and Assumptions

The strategy addresses enterprise workloads that:

- Exchange telemetry and transactional data across providers.
- Require low operational overhead and elastic scalability.
- Must respect region-level data governance and organizational policies.
- May operate in or interoperate with mainland China regions and networks.

Assumptions:

- Cross-cloud communication primarily uses public HTTPS endpoints hardened with Web App and API Protection (WAAP) controls; private interconnects are optional and outside the PoC.

- Workloads are designed for eventual consistency and idempotent processing.
- Where a managed service lacks strict equivalences, the design adds app-level compensations.

Objectives and Quality Attributes

Grounded in chapter 3, the strategy optimizes for:

- **Portability:** Minimize provider-specific surface in application code and IaC; favor standard interfaces.
- **Resilience:** Active-active or warm standby across clouds; fault isolation by domain; rapid failover.
- **Compliance:** Region pinning, encryption, access control, and evidence generation by default.
- **Operational Efficiency:** Serverless bias and managed services; automation via IaC; policy-as-code guardrails.
- **Cost Awareness:** Use pay-per-use services; use budget and utilization controls (FinOps).

Key performance indicators (KPIs) for evaluation (collected in chapter 7 where feasible):

- Portability ratio (features expressed natively vs. cross-cloud IaC).
- Time-to-deploy and destroy lead time.
- End-to-end latency per stream.
- Compliance coverage (encryption, logging, auditability).

5.2 Reference Compute Models

A review of multi-cloud reference architectures highlights three dominant compute patterns [58, pp. 72–79]:

- **Managed VM Architectures:** Use managed virtual machines (e.g., Amazon EC2; Alibaba ECS) with configuration management and golden images. Suitable for legacy workloads or where kernel/OS control is required; highest operational burden.
- **Container-based Architectures:** Use Kubernetes (EKS on AWS; ACK on Alibaba Cloud) as the portability and orchestration layer. Strong abstraction for microservices; requires platform and security expertise.
- **Serverless Architectures:** Favor fully managed services and functions (AWS Lambda; Alibaba Function Compute), event-driven processing, and IaC-driven automation. Lowest ops overhead; service disparity can introduce portability gaps.

As summarized in Table 5.1, each pattern offers distinct advantages. For the evaluated IoT telemetry workload and comparable event-driven systems, a *serverless-first* baseline with selective containerization for gaps balances portability, resilience, and operational efficiency.

Feature	Managed VM	Container	Serverless
Portability	Medium	High	High if APIs align
Operational Overhead	High	Medium	Low
Scalability	Medium	High	Very High
Cost effectiveness	Low	Medium	High (pay-per-use)
Vendor Lock-in	Medium	Low	Variable (often high)
Compliance Control	High	Medium	Low (strong provider baselines)
Time-to-Market	Medium	Medium	Fast

Table 5.1: Comparison of multi-cloud compute models [58, pp. 72–79]

5.3 Target State and Guiding Principles

The target state consolidates the strategy's intent into implementable guidelines. It defines preferred services, fallbacks, and cross-cutting principles used to assess trade-offs throughout the PoC.

Serverless-First With Pragmatic Fallbacks

Building on chapter 4, the target state favors:

1. **Stateless compute via functions** for ingestion, transformation, and integration logic.
2. **Managed messaging** for decoupling, buffering, and fanout (provider equivalents).
3. **Object storage** as the durable system-of-record for telemetry (provider equivalents).
4. **API mediation** via managed gateways for external HTTP APIs and cross-cloud adapter endpoints; *device telemetry ingress uses MQTT brokers with mutual TLS*.
5. **Containers or VMs** only when a serverless gap materially affects parity, performance, or compliance.

Design Principles

- **Event First:** Prefer asynchronous, idempotent integration with dead-letter handling and replay.

- **Secure by Default:** TLS 1.2+, encryption at rest, least privilege, and private endpoints where possible.
- **Policy as Code:** Enforce guardrails (Service control policies (SCPs)/Resource Directory policies) and IaC validations (e.g., OPA or native) [125].
- **Data Minimization and Residency:** Move only what is necessary; pseudonymize or tokenize prior to cross-border transfer.
- **Observability Everywhere:** Centralize logs/metrics/traces; capture evidence for audits.
- **Operational Simplicity:** Optimize for automation, blast-radius isolation, and clear runbooks.

5.4 Architecture Design for AWS–Alibaba Cloud Interoperability

This section presents the logical blueprint, service mappings, and cross-cutting patterns for interoperability. It separates the *data plane* (ingestion, processing, storage, distribution) from the *control plane* (identity, policy, observability, automation), mirroring the concerns defined in the methodology. Figure 5.1 summarizes the reference architecture.

Overview and Logical Blueprint

Each provider hosts a complete, loosely coupled slice of the data plane. Telemetry ingress uses MQTT with mutual TLS. Messages then flow through two concurrent streams:

- **Buffered storage stream** for durable, replayable processing.
- **Real-time distribution stream** for low-latency fanout to controlled HTTPS adapters.

Cross-cloud interactions are exposed only through authenticated interfaces (HTTPS with signature verification or mTLS, or MQTT over TLS), with optional CDN fronting public APIs. On the control plane, automation and synchronization are achieved through infrastructure-as-code (AWS CDK and Alibaba ROS CDK).

Component Catalog and Mappings

Key components:

- **Ingestion:**
 - AWS: IoT Core MQTT broker and rules (*device ingress over MQTT/mTLS*).
 - Alibaba: ThingsBoard on ECS (mutual TLS MQTT) or ApsaraMQ for MQTT where feasible.

Figure 5.1: Reference architecture for serverless-first multi-cloud interoperability. Each provider hosts an equivalent slice of the data plane, with infrastructure deployed and synchronized via the chosen CDK framework.

- **Buffering and Decoupling:**
 - AWS: SQS (with DLQ and visibility tuning).
 - Alibaba: Simple Message Queue (SMQ/MNS) Queue (DLQ via dead-letter topic or error queue).
- **Compute:**
 - AWS: Lambda for transformation and routing.
 - Alibaba: Function Compute (FC) for equivalent roles.
- **Fanout/Distribution:**
 - AWS: SNS topic with HTTPS subscription to external adapter (signature verification).
 - Alibaba: SMQ Topic with HTTP(S) subscription to external adapter (signed delivery or shared-secret headers).
- **Durable Storage:**
 - AWS: S3 with encryption and lifecycle policies.
 - Alibaba: OSS with encryption and lifecycle.
- **Ingress Mediation:** Managed API gateways/load balancers for HTTP-based external APIs and adapters; device telemetry ingress is via MQTT brokers.
- **Observability:** CloudWatch (logs, metrics, alarms) on AWS; Simple Log Service (SLS) and ActionTrail on Alibaba Cloud.

Justifications and notable differences

- **Queue semantics:** AWS SQS offers FIFO and exactly-once processing modes; Alibaba SMQ lacks strict FIFO in the same form. Use idempotency keys and per-partition ordering keys to approximate ordering if required.
- **Fanout verification:** AWS SNS signatures can be verified by the adapter; SMQ provides signed delivery options or shared-secret headers. Both paths are enforced with origin validation middleware.

Event-Driven Design Patterns

Regarding event-driven design patterns [126]:

- **Outbox/Ingest Pattern:** Treat ingestion as the authoritative write; emit downstream events asynchronously.
- **Idempotency and De-duplication:** Stamp events with deterministic IDs (e.g., deviceId-timestamp) and maintain idempotency keys.

- **Dead-Letter and Reprocessing:** Route failures to Dead letter queues (DLQs); provide replay tooling via IaC.
- **Event Versioning:** Use versioning and consumer-driven tests to protect cross-cloud interfaces.

Networking and Edge

- **Segmentation:** Separate VPC/VSwitch per environment and sensitivity; lock down security groups; use private endpoints for PaaS where available [58, pp. 24–27].
- **Edge Delivery:** Employ CDN (CloudFront/Alibaba CDN) for external APIs or UIs; use origin access controls and signed URLs/cookies [127].
- **China Considerations:** For mainland delivery, ensure ICP filing/licensing; avoid cross-border acceleration that violates regulatory constraints [33].

5.5 Infrastructure as Code: Tooling and Migration Design

Infrastructure as Code (IaC) is the primary lever for reproducibility, governance, and portability. The strategy evaluates provider-native CDKs (AWS CDK; ROS CDK) alongside cloud-agnostic Terraform/CDKTF to balance expressiveness against lock-in.

Tooling Options and Rationale

We evaluate:

- **Provider-Native IaC:** Deep integration, faster access to new services, concise constructs; higher lock-in and lower portability.
- **Cloud-Agnostic IaC:** Common workflow and ecosystem; may lag in coverage or require verbose, provider-specific modules.

Design choice for this thesis. Implement the reference architecture using provider-native CDKs (AWS CDK, ROS CDK) and CDK for Terraform (CDKTF) targeting Terraform/OpenTofu providers. The evaluation focuses on:

- **Structural Portability:** Compare provider-native synthesized templates (CloudFormation vs. ROS) and Terraform/OpenTofu JSON resource graphs; compute resource/category overlaps and a heuristic portability score.
- **Migration Effort:** Report authored IaC line counts and deploy/destroy lead times; capture qualitative rework required to move between toolchains.
- **Maintainability:** Qualitative assessment of readability, module reuse, and ergonomics, complemented by lines-of-code and synthesis/apply stability.

- **Governance (qualitative):** Document baseline policy-as-code posture and CI validations; deep OPA/Sentinel integration is noted as future work and is not quantitatively evaluated in the PoC.

Abstractions

Abstraction layers:

- **Constructs/Modules:** Encapsulate messaging+compute+storage as a reusable unit with well-defined inputs/outputs.
- **Environment Profiles:** Parameterize regions, accounts, and compliance flags (allowed/denied regions).
- **Policy Libraries:** Reusable IAM/RAM policy snippets with linting and tests.

Migration Trade-offs and Patterns

- **Adapter Pattern:** Wrap provider-specific resources behind a local interface (e.g., Queue abstraction mapping to SQS or SMQ).
- **Conditional Compilation:** Feature flags in IaC to include/exclude resources by provider or region.
- **Bridging Gaps:** Where Terraform providers lag, use provisioners or external scripts judiciously; track technical debt via architecture decision records (ADRs).

5.6 Security and Compliance Strategy for Multi-Cloud Workloads

Security follows least privilege and zero-trust within provider shared responsibility models. Controls are applied consistently across clouds and enforced through IaC, with evidence captured for audits and regulatory reviews.

Security Best Practices

- **Federated IAM:** Centralize workforce identity (SAML/OIDC) with short-lived credentials; enforce MFA and least privilege [128, pp. 78–81].
- **Device Identity:** Mutual TLS with X.509 for MQTT; managed policies (IoT policy in AWS; TB credential mapping or ApsaraMQ for MQTT auth).
- **Encryption:** TLS 1.2+ in transit; envelope encryption for sensitive data [128, pp. 478–480].
- **API and Edge Security:** API gateway mediation with JWT validation or mTLS; WAF rulesets; rate limiting and request validation.

- **Network Segmentation:** Isolate environments by VPC/VSwitch; private endpoints for PaaS; egress restrictions [128, pp. 311–313].
- **Observability and IR:** Centralized logs/metrics/traces; immutable audit trails; cross-cloud incident playbooks [58, pp. 189-190].
- **Policy as Code:** Organization policies (SCPs/Resource Directory) and CI checks to prevent drift [58, pp. 221-223].

Compliance for Cross-Border Data Transfers

Ensuring compliance in cross-border data transfers requires privacy-first design principles that balance regulatory obligations with security and performance. As Mokale [129] notes, traditional centralized models expose user data to surveillance, breaches, and regulatory violations, making privacy-centric approaches essential for sustainable global content distribution. Key strategies include:

- **Encryption and Key Management:** Employ end-to-end encryption (E2EE) with customer-managed keys, usage logging, and automated key rotation. Where required by law, integrate external hardware security modules (HSMs) to strengthen sovereignty over encryption materials.
- **Geo-fencing and Policy Enforcement:** Define allow/deny rules in Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC) stacks and apply organization-wide policies that prevent data transfers to restricted regions. Regulatory-aware data routing mechanisms help ensure that information stays within compliant jurisdictions.
- **Data Minimization and De-identification:** Reduce exposure by pseudonymizing or tokenizing personal data prior to transfer. Re-identification keys must remain within the originating jurisdiction to comply with data localization mandates.
- **Transfer Governance:** Maintain standardized contractual safeguards such as Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs), International Data Transfer Agreements (IDTAs), Transfer Impact Assessments (TIAs), and Data Processing Agreements (DPAs). Automating audit evidence collection improves compliance assurance and reduces operational burden.
- **Edge and CDN Controls:** Restrict content delivery origins and enforce signed URLs or cookies to ensure controlled distribution. For specific regions such as China, compliance with local requirements (e.g., ICP licensing) is necessary to maintain lawful access.

By integrating these practices into privacy-first architectures, organizations can achieve regulatory compliance, enhance user trust, and reduce the risks associated with cross-border data transfers.

5.7 Deployment Models and Patterns

Selecting deployment patterns requires balancing portability, latency, cost, and regulatory constraints. The following models and workflows align with the compute strategy.

Model Selection Rationale

- **Serverless:** Prefer for stateless APIs, event processing, and data pipelines where parity exists.
- **Container:** Use for stateful/complex workloads, custom runtimes, or performance-sensitive services.
- **Hybrid:** Combine as needed, incrementally migrating toward cloud-native services.

Traffic and Resilience Patterns

To ground the architecture in reproducible practice, the following traffic management and resilience patterns synthesize guidance from Datla [130] on multi-zone redundancy and self-healing operations for always-on insurance systems. They are technology-agnostic, prioritize fault isolation and rapid recovery, and can be tailored to workload criticality.

- **Active-Active:** Run stateless, read-focused, and idempotent request paths across regions or availability zones (and, where appropriate, across multiple cloud providers); direct user traffic by measured latency and user geography using the Domain Name System (DNS) or global traffic managers with health-based routing.
- **Active-Passive (warm standby):** Maintain a warm standby with continuously synchronized configuration and data, plus automated runbooks; practice failover and failback through Domain Name System (DNS) changes and configuration flags in regular failure-simulation exercises.
- **Blue/Green and Canary:** Advance releases safely within each cloud provider, then gradually increase cross-region or cross-cloud traffic to confirm functional and performance parity; trigger automatic rollback if latency, error rates, or throughput objectives degrade.
- **Data Disaster Recovery:** Replicate object and log data with encryption and immutability across regions; verify Recovery Point Objective (RPO) and Recovery Time Objective (RTO) through scheduled full and partial restores and region-level failover tests.

Deployment Workflows

Cloud-Native Deployment

1. Define resources (functions, storage, APIs/ingress, events) using AWS CDK, ROS CDK, and/or Terraform.
2. Deploy compute and expose via API Gateway/function URLs/load balancers as appropriate.
3. Configure event sources, DLQs, and idempotency keys; prefer private integrations for east-west traffic.

Container-Based Deployment

1. Package workloads as OCI images with SBOMs and signing; scan in CI.
2. Deploy to EKS/ACK via IaC/Helm/manifests; enforce Pod Security Standards and network policies.
3. Optionally integrate a service mesh for mTLS, traffic shaping, and policy; expose via ingress to managed load balancers or API gateway/CDN.

5.8 Risks and Mitigations

The most significant risks and corresponding mitigations are summarized in Table 5.2 to guide implementation choices and operational preparedness.

Risk	Description	Mitigation
Service Disparity	Missing features or differing services	App-level idempotency; abstraction modules; selective container or VM fallback
Compliance Drift	Region misdeployments; weak evidence	Geo-fencing in IaC; org policies; automated evidence capture
Operational Overhead	Parallel stacks increase complexity	Serverless bias; shared modules; unified runbooks; observability standards
Cross-Border Constraints	Transfer approvals; ICP requirements	Data minimization; tokenization; local processing; legal arrangements (SCC/IDTA)
Vendor Lock-in	Native constructs hard to port	CDKTF modules; adapter pattern; keep business logic portable

Table 5.2: Top risks and mitigations for the multi-cloud strategy.

5.9 Summary

This chapter established a serverless-first, event-driven multi-cloud strategy with explicit controls for identity, security, networking, and compliance. It justified component choices based on chapter 4, operationalized the methodology of chapter 3, and produced an architecture suitable for empirical validation. The next chapter implements this blueprint on AWS and Alibaba Cloud, using both native and cross-cloud IaC, and evaluates portability, effort, and parity against the defined key performance indicators (KPIs).

Chapter 6

Proof-of-Concept Implementation

This chapter presents the practical realization of the minimal IoT multi-cloud stack. The proof-of-concept (PoC) deployment demonstrates that a representative IoT workload can operate in parallel on AWS and Alibaba Cloud using equivalent managed services, while preserving functional parity and adhering to security best practices. The discussion begins with an overview of the workload and its architecture, followed by implementation details for each platform, observations on portability, and the results of basic validation. A step-by-step deployment guide is included in section 6.6, with a dedicated ThingsBoard ingestion section for the Alibaba Cloud implementation in section 6.6. Alternative deployments using CDK for Terraform (CDKTF) are covered in section 6.7. Certificate handling for AWS IoT Core, the external adapter, and ThingsBoard is covered in section 6.8.

6.1 Representative Workload and Reference Architecture

The PoC centres on an IoT telemetry ingestion and processing pipeline deployed in parallel on AWS and Alibaba Cloud. The architecture follows established IoT-to-cloud integration patterns, combining managed messaging, serverless compute, and durable object storage. It is designed with a high degree of modularity so that individual components can be replaced or extended without requiring a complete system redesign.

Telemetry is generated by simulated industrial devices and transmitted over MQTT to the cloud-based ingestion layer. Upon arrival, each message is processed in *two parallel streams*, each optimised for a specific operational objective.

The **buffered storage stream** implements durable, decoupled processing. In the AWS deployment, AWS IoT Core routes messages via an IoT rule to an Amazon SQS queue. A Lambda function subscribed to the queue retrieves each message, applies lightweight transformations and enrichment, and writes the processed data to an encrypted Amazon S3 bucket for archival and batch-oriented analysis. In the Alibaba Cloud deployment, *ThingsBoard provides MQTT ingestion* using mutual TLS (X.509

client authentication) and forwards events via a Rule Chain to a Flask adapter running on ECS. The adapter uses the Alibaba Cloud SDK to publish each message to Simple Message Queue (SMQ) in queue mode. Function Compute then consumes messages from the queue and writes processed results to an encrypted OSS bucket. This stream ensures that all telemetry is reliably persisted regardless of downstream latency or connectivity issues.

The **real-time distribution stream** enables low-latency forwarding of selected events to an external adapter for WAN integration testing. On AWS, IoT Core routes messages directly to a Lambda function, which performs minimal preprocessing and then publishes the event to an Amazon SNS topic using the internal SDK endpoint. The SNS topic is configured with an HTTP(S) subscription targeting the external adapter endpoint. SNS handles the delivery, including retries, backoff, and at-least-once semantics. On Alibaba Cloud, the Flask adapter (invoked by the ThingsBoard Rule Chain) publishes selected events to an SMQ topic, which is configured with an HTTP(S) delivery subscription to the external adapter. In the AWS case, the subscription endpoint must be confirmed before it becomes active; both platforms rely on TLS to secure data in transit.

Both processing streams operate concurrently, enabling the system to achieve two goals: (i) durable archival of all telemetry for later processing, and (ii) rapid dissemination of selected events to external systems. This dual-path design also enables comparative analysis of throughput, end-to-end latency, and fault tolerance for batch-oriented versus real-time delivery modes.

Operationally, HTTP(S) subscriptions to the external adapter require secure endpoint configuration and origin validation (e.g., signature verification or mutual TLS). The adapter must be idempotent to cope with possible duplicate deliveries, and robust retry policies are essential for correctness under transient network failures.

Rationale for Workload Selection

This workload was chosen because it closely matches a common IoT-to-cloud communication pattern used in production systems. It incorporates diverse cloud primitives like MQTT ingestion, queue-based decoupling, pub/sub messaging, serverless compute, and object storage, enabling a meaningful service-parity comparison. The design's modularity makes it adaptable to scalability experiments and alternative service configurations without structural redesign.

Reference Architecture Diagram

Figure 6.1 shows the minimal IoT stack for both clouds, including the two processing streams, service mappings, and message flows. On Alibaba Cloud, MQTT ingestion is handled by ThingsBoard (with X.509 client authentication), which forwards messages via its Rule Chain to the Flask adapter; the adapter then publishes to SMQ (queue and topic) using the Alibaba Cloud SDK.

Figure 6.1: Reference architecture of the minimal IoT multi-cloud stack. Messages are processed in two parallel streams: a buffered storage stream and a real-time distribution stream. On Alibaba Cloud, ThingsBoard performs MQTT ingestion (X.509 mTLS) and forwards to a Flask adapter, which publishes to SMQ.

Service Mapping, Security, and Compliance Considerations

The mapping of equivalent services across AWS and Alibaba Cloud is summarized in Table 6.1. Both stacks implement the same functional primitives—ingestion, queue-based decoupling, serverless compute, pub/sub messaging, and object storage—to ensure workload parity across providers.

Component	AWS	Alibaba Cloud
IoT Ingestion	AWS IoT Core	ThingsBoard + Rule Chain + Flask Adapter
Object Storage	Amazon S3	Alibaba OSS
Serverless Compute	AWS Lambda	Function Compute (FC)
Queue Messaging	Amazon SQS	SMQ (Queue)
Pub/Sub Messaging	Amazon SNS	SMQ (Topic)
IAM/Identity	IAM	RAM
Monitoring/Logging	CloudWatch	Log Service

Table 6.1: Service mapping for the minimal IoT stack across AWS and Alibaba Cloud.

Figure 6.2 complements the logical reference architecture (Figure 6.1) by illustrating the end-to-end data flow with explicit security and compliance boundaries. The diagram highlights how device telemetry moves from test data generators into each cloud's ingestion layer (AWS IoT Core or ThingsBoard) using **mutual TLS with X.509 client certificates**. Once inside the provider perimeter, messages flow only over **encrypted internal channels** (HTTPS/TLS) between processing components and storage services (Amazon S3 or Alibaba OSS).

Security controls are applied consistently across both providers:

- **Transport security:** All MQTT device connectivity enforces mutual TLS with X.509 certificates; all inter-service communications use HTTPS/TLS (1.2+).
- **Access control:** IAM and RAM policies enforce least privilege for compute, messaging, and storage components.
- **Network boundaries:** WAN endpoints have clear boundaries, restricting inbound access to known IPs via security-group whitelisting.
- **Data protection at rest:** Both S3 and OSS buckets can use server-side encryption with provider-managed keys [84], [85].
- **Auditability:** CloudWatch and Log Service centralize event logs for compliance monitoring and forensic analysis.

From a compliance perspective, Figure 6.2 makes visible the critical safeguards: (i) all telemetry in transit is encrypted, (ii) mutual authentication ensures device identity, (iii) data at rest resides exclusively in managed storage services, and (iv) external data transfers (e.g., HTTPS access from CSPs to external endpoints) are explicitly marked.

Figure 6.2: Data flow and security boundaries for the PoC IoT workload across AWS and Alibaba Cloud. Encrypted protocols (MQTT/TLS with X.509, HTTPS/TLS), different networks (WAN vs internal), data reception and processing, and storage are explicitly shown for compliance verification.

6.2 Implementation on AWS

The AWS deployment uses the AWS Cloud Development Kit (CDK) with a *Python* application, enabling a single, version-controlled IaC definition for the entire stack. IoT Core rules are configured to forward incoming messages to both SQS (for the buffered storage stream) and SNS (for the real-time distribution stream). In the first stream, Lambda functions process messages from SQS and store results in S3. In the second stream, Lambda functions publish directly to SNS, which then delivers to the external adapter via an HTTP(S) subscription.

The S3 bucket is configured with encryption and lifecycle rules. IAM roles restrict permissions to the minimum required for each component. Certificate provisioning for IoT devices (Thing, keys, and certificate) is performed in the AWS Management Console as described in section 6.8. A Thing is the cloud representation of a physical device and is used to manage secure access in IoT Core [104]. Deployment follows the standard CDK process: set up a Python virtual environment, install dependencies, synthesise CloudFormation templates, and deploy via the CDK CLI.

Challenges included fine-tuning IAM permissions for IoT Core → SQS/SNS and verifying MQTT rule SQL statements. Validation involved generating telemetry, confirming delivery to both streams, checking object storage in S3, and verifying CloudWatch logs.

6.3 Implementation on Alibaba Cloud

The Alibaba Cloud deployment is defined using the Resource Orchestration Service (ROS) CDK with a *Python* application. MQTT ingestion is provided by a ThingsBoard Community Edition instance running on ECS. Devices connect to ThingsBoard over MQTT using X.509 client certificates (mutual TLS). ThingsBoard forwards messages through a Rule Chain to a Flask-based adapter hosted on ECS. The adapter uses the Alibaba Cloud SDK to publish to SMQ in both queue mode (buffered storage stream) and topic mode (real-time distribution stream). Function Compute consumes from the queue and writes processed data to OSS; the SMQ topic is configured with an HTTP(S) subscription to the external adapter for WAN integration testing.

RAM policies enforce least-privilege access for Function Compute and the adapter to SMQ, OSS, and Log Service. The OSS bucket is encrypted. Deployment mirrors AWS: set up a Python virtual environment, install dependencies, synthesise templates, and deploy via the ROS CDK CLI.

Challenges included configuring the ThingsBoard Rule Chain for reliable delivery to the adapter, tuning RAM policies for SMQ publish permissions from ECS, and SMQ topic HTTP delivery. Validation confirmed correct data flow in both streams.

6.4 Portability and Migration Effort

Migrating from AWS CDK to Alibaba ROS CDK required adapting the ingestion design. AWS provides a native IoT ingestion service (IoT Core), whereas on Alibaba Cloud this PoC uses ThingsBoard for MQTT ingestion and a Rule Chain to integrate with the Flask adapter, which then publishes to SMQ. Messaging semantics differ, because AWS separates SQS and SNS, while SMQ handles both queue and topic modes. Function triggers also vary between Lambda and Function Compute.

The migration involved reworking IaC definitions in Python, adjusting IAM/RAM, integrating ThingsBoard into the path, and modifying deployment logic. This effort will be quantified in code change percentage in chapter 7. The experience underlines the need for clearly defined and documented IaC components in multi-cloud deployments.

6.5 Basic Validation: Functionality, Security, and Logging

Validation confirmed that both platforms correctly ingest, process, store, and distribute telemetry through the two streams. On AWS, the SNS HTTP subscription successfully delivered to the external adapter; on Alibaba Cloud, SMQ topic HTTP delivery achieved the same, with events originating from ThingsBoard → Rule Chain → Flask adapter → SMQ. Security checks verified TLS encryption, encryption at rest, and correct execution roles. Logging on CloudWatch and Log Service confirmed expected event flows. Minor differences in trigger timing were mitigated with retry logic and buffering.

6.6 Step-by-Step Deployment Guide

This section provides reproducible, end-to-end deployment steps for both clouds. It assumes a single mono-repo with three IaC packages (AWS CDK, Alibaba ROS CDK, and CDK for Terraform), all authored in Python, plus application code (simulator, adapter, functions).

Prerequisites and Accounts

Common

- Python 3.7+ with venv and pip.
- Node.js LTS for the CDK/ROS CDK/CDKTF CLIs (language-agnostic CLIs).
- OpenTofu LTS and CDK for Terraform CLI.
- X.509 PKI materials for devices:
 - Per-device private key and certificate (PEM).
 - Trusted root CA(s) for AWS IoT Core (ATS) and for ThingsBoard's MQTT endpoint.

- For ThingsBoard, either a device certificate registered in TB or a trusted issuing CA configured in TB device credentials.

AWS

- AWS account with privileges to bootstrap and deploy.
- AWS CLI v2 configured (`aws configure`) with region (e.g., `eu-central-1`).
- AWS CDK CLI installed (`npm i -g aws-cdk`).
- An AWS IoT Thing and associated active certificate and keys created via the AWS Console (download and store the device certificate, private key, and the ATS root CA).

Alibaba Cloud

- Alibaba Cloud account with permissions for Access Key, ECS, OSS, Function Compute, and SMQ.
- Alibaba Cloud CLI configured (`aliyun configure`) with region.
- ROS CDK CLI installed (`npm i -g @alicloud/ros-cdk-cli`)

Repository Layout and Configuration

Assuming a directory structure:

```
repo/
  aws_minimal_iot_stack_cf/      # AWS CDK app
  aws_minimal_iot_stack_tf/     # CDKTF app targeting AWS provider
  ali_minimal_iot_stack_ros/    # ROS CDK app
  ali_minimal_iot_stack_tf/    # CDKTF app targeting Alicloud provider
  misc/
    flask_relay_server/        # Flask relay server (for Thingsboard)
    flask_notification_adapter/ # Flask adapter (External HTTP endpoint)
```

Set environment values:

```
# ALIBABA_CLOUD_ACCESS_KEY_ID=...
# ALIBABA_CLOUD_ACCESS_KEY_SECRET=...
# aws_access_key_id=...
# aws_secret_access_key=...
# aws_session_token=...
```

Initialization: One-Time Per Account/Region

AWS CDK Bootstrap (Python app)

```
cd aws_minimal_iot_stack_cf
python -m venv .venv && source .venv/bin/activate
pip install -r requirements.txt
cdk bootstrap aws://$AWS_ACCOUNT_ID/$AWS_REGION
```

ROS CDK Initialization (Python app)

```
cd ali_minimal_iot_stack_ros
python -m venv .venv && source .venv/bin/activate
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

CDK for Terraform backends (Python apps) Decide state backends [46]:

- AWS: S3 backend or local (default) for PoC.
- Alibaba: OSS backend or local (default) for PoC.

AWS Deployment Steps (AWS CDK, Python)

1. Provision Thing and device certificate in the Console

- (a) In AWS IoT Core Console: *Manage* → *Things* → *Create single thing*. Create the Thing.
- (b) Generate a new certificate and keys. Download the device certificate, private key, and AmazonRootCA1 (ATS) root CA. Activate the certificate. Do not attach a policy yet.

2. Install dependencies and synthesise

```
cd aws_minimal_iot_stack_cf
source .venv/bin/activate
pip install -r requirements.txt
cdk synth
```

3. Deploy the stack

```
cdk deploy
```

Ensure the stack defines the IoT policy required for device publish/subscribe and connect (the stack typically outputs the policy name/ARN).

4. Attach the policy to the certificate in the Console (more details in 6.8)

- (a) IoT Core Console: *Security* → *Certificates* → select your certificate → *Actions* → *Attach policy*. Choose the policy created by the stack.
- (b) If not already linked, attach the certificate to the Thing: *Actions* → *Attach thing*.

5. Configure SNS HTTPS subscription

- (a) Ensure the external adapter endpoint is reachable over HTTPS and presents a valid certificate.
- (b) Create and confirm the subscription as needed.

6. Run the MQTT simulator against IoT Core (X.509)

```
cd ../simulator
python -m venv .venv && source .venv/bin/activate
pip install -r requirements.txt
python simulate.py --broker <AWS_IOT_ENDPOINT> \
  --topic iot/telemetry/device1 \
  --cert device1.cert.pem --key device1.private.key --ca AmazonRootCA1.pem
```

7. Validate

- SQS receives messages; Lambda consumes and writes to S3.
- SNS delivers events to the external adapter (HTTP 2xx in logs).
- CloudWatch logs show expected processing.

Alibaba Cloud Deployment Steps (ROS CDK, Python) + ThingsBoard

1. Deploy the stack

```
cd ali_minimal_iot_stack_ros
source .venv/bin/activate
pip install -r requirements.txt
ros-cdk synth
ros-cdk deploy
```

2. Configure ThingsBoard for MQTT ingestion with X.509

- (a) In ThingsBoard, set device credentials to *X.509 Certificate*:
 - Upload the device certificate (fingerprint matching) or register a trusted issuing CA.
- (b) Ensure MQTT over TLS (port 8883) requests and validates client certificates.
- (c) Provide the TB server certificate chain CA to clients so they can verify the server.

3. Create a ThingsBoard Rule Chain to call the Flask adapter

- (a) In TB Rule Engine, add a “REST API Call” node targeting the adapter HTTPS endpoint.
- (b) Map the incoming telemetry to the adapter's expected JSON schema.
- (c) Route success and failure paths with retries/backoff as needed.

4. Adapter publishes to SMQ

- Configure RAM credentials and endpoints for:
 - SMQ Queue (buffered storage stream).
 - SMQ Topic (real-time distribution stream).
- Verify RAM policies include `mns:SendMessage` and `mns:PublishMessage`.

5. Configure SMQ Topic HTTP(S) subscription

- Create an HTTP(S) subscription on the SMQ topic to `$EXTERNAL_ADAPTER_URL`.
- Enable retries, backoff, and at-least-once semantics; record signing/secret headers for origin validation.

6. Run the MQTT simulator against ThingsBoard (X.509)

```
cd ../simulator
source .venv/bin/activate
python simulate.py --broker <TB_MQTT_ENDPOINT>:8883 \
  --topic iot/telemetry/device1 \
  --cert device1.cert.pem --key device1.private.key --ca tb-server-ca.pem
```

7. Validate

- TB receives MQTT telemetry via X.509 mTLS; Rule Chain triggers adapter calls (2xx responses).
- SMQ Queue receives messages; FC writes objects to OSS.
- SMQ Topic delivers events to the external adapter (HTTP 2xx).
- Log Service logs show expected processing.

ThingsBoard on Alibaba Cloud (ingestion and optional dashboards)

ThingsBoard Community Edition on ECS serves as the MQTT ingress layer with X.509 mutual TLS for device authentication. Optionally, it also provides dashboards for real-time and historical views. No intermediate bridging component is used in this PoC: messages flow TB (MQTT, X.509 mTLS) → Rule Chain → Flask adapter → SMQ.

Provisioning and runtime

- Deploy ThingsBoard on ECS (containerized or package-based); for this PoC, restrict access via security groups to known IPs.
- Use PostgreSQL (e.g., ApsaraDB RDS) as the backing database.
- Expose MQTT over TLS (port 8883) with client certificate validation enabled.

Rule Chain visualization Figure 6.3 illustrates the extended Rule Chain used in this PoC. Most nodes correspond to the default ThingsBoard Root Rule Chain (e.g., attribute storage, time-series persistence, and logging). The custom contributions are the two additional REST API call nodes, *Send to SMQ Relay* and *Send to FC3 Trigger*, which forward telemetry to the Flask adapter for integration with Alibaba Cloud services. This extension ensures that device telemetry is routed reliably into both the buffered storage and the real-time distribution streams.

Figure 6.3: Extended ThingsBoard Rule Chain. The two custom REST API nodes *Send to SMQ Relay* and *Send to FC3 Trigger* provide integration with Alibaba Cloud messaging and Function Compute.

6.7 Alternative Deployment: CDK for Terraform

To demonstrate tooling portability, the PoC includes a parallel implementation using CDK for Terraform. CDKTF compiles Python constructs into Terraform JSON configuration and deploys via the OpenTofu CLI (open source fork of Terraform, functionally almost identical), allowing a consistent IaC authoring model across providers.

Prerequisites

- OpenTofu LTS and CDKTF CLI installed:

```
npm i -g cdktf
```

- Providers:

- AWS: registry.opentofu.org/hashicorp/aws.

- Alibaba Cloud: registry.opentofu.org/hashicorp/alicloud.

Project scaffolding (Python)

```
# AWS
cd aws_minimal_iot_stack_tf
source .venv/bin/activate
cdktf init --template=python --local
pip install -r requirements.txt
cdktf get
```

```
# Alibaba Cloud
cd ali_minimal_iot_stack_tf
source .venv/bin/activate
cdktf init --template=python --local
pip install -r requirements.txt
cdktf get
```

AWS Stack (CDKTF, Python)

- Resources:
 - S3 bucket (encryption, lifecycle).
 - SQS queue, dead-letter queue.
 - SNS topic and HTTPS subscription (confirmation may be out-of-band).
 - Lambda functions (`aws_lambda_function`) with IAM roles/policies.
 - IoT Core rule (`aws_iot_topic_rule`) routing to SQS and/or Lambda.
- Commands:

```
cd cdktf/aws_py
source .venv/bin/activate
pip install -r requirements.txt
cdktf synth
cdktf diff
cdktf deploy
```

Alibaba Cloud Stack (CDKTF, Python)

- Resources:
 - OSS bucket with encryption.
 - SMQ (previously MNS) queue and topic with HTTP endpoint subscription.
 - Function Compute service, function, and triggers.
 - ECS instances (ThingsBoard + Flask adapter).
 - RAM roles/policies for FC and ECS to access SMQ/OSS/Logs.

- Commands:

```
cd cdktf/ali_py
source .venv/bin/activate
pip install -r requirements.txt
cdktf synth
cdktf diff
cdktf deploy
```

State and pipelines

- CDKTF-only: Terraform/OpenTofu keeps a state file. For a solo PoC, keep state local (default) or use a simple remote bucket (S3/OSS) without locking; just avoid concurrent applies. AWS CDK and Alibaba ROS CDK do not use Terraform state.
- Optional remote state: S3 (AWS) or OSS (Alibaba) without DynamoDB/OTS locking, or use Terraform Cloud for managed state and locking (no DynamoDB/OTS needed).
- Optional CI: run `cdktf synth` and `cdktf diff` on pull requests to preview; run `cdktf deploy` on main to apply. Pipelines do not require DynamoDB/OTS.
- Simplest local flow: run `cdktf synth`, `cdktf diff`, and `cdktf deploy` from your workstation.

Note on parity: Some resources (e.g., SNS HTTPS subscription confirmation) involve out-of-band steps; CDKTF can create the subscription, but confirmation requires the endpoint to respond appropriately.

6.8 Certificate Handling and Key Management

This section details certificate handling for AWS IoT Core device connectivity, HTTPS delivery to the external adapter, and TLS for the ThingsBoard stack.

AWS IoT Core: Device Certificates and Policies (Console-driven)

Overview Devices authenticate to AWS IoT Core using mutual TLS with X.509 client certificates. In this PoC, Things and certificates are provisioned via the AWS Management Console, and the IoT policy is created by the CDK stack and attached afterwards in the Console.

Procedure

- 1. Create Thing and device certificate in the Console:**
 - IoT Core Console → Manage → Things → Create single thing.
 - Generate a new certificate and keys; download the certificate, private key, and AmazonRootCA1 (ATS) root CA. Activate the certificate.
 - Skip attaching a policy at creation time (it will be attached after the stack deploys).
- 2. Deploy the CDK stack that defines the IoT policy.** Record the output policy name/ARN.
- 3. Attach the policy to the certificate in the Console:**
 - Security → Certificates → select the certificate → Actions → Attach policy → choose the policy created by the stack.
- 4. Attach the certificate to the Thing** (if not already attached):
 - Actions → Attach thing → select the Thing created earlier.
- 5. Obtain the IoT data endpoint** (Console or CLI) and configure the device client with endpoint, device certificate, private key, and ATS root CA.

Rotation and revocation

- To rotate, create and activate a new certificate in the Console, attach the same policy, update the device, then disable and revoke the old certificate.

External Adapter: HTTPS, Signature Validation, and Optional mTLS

Origin validation

- **AWS SNS:** verify message authenticity using the SNS signature (SigningCertURL + Signature + Message/MessageAttributes). Implement the standard verification flow in the adapter; reject invalid requests.

- **Alibaba SMQ topic HTTP delivery:** enable signing/secret headers if available; verify HMAC or platform-provided signature in the adapter middleware.

Optional mutual TLS (not implemented)

- If corporate policy requires mTLS, terminate at a reverse proxy (e.g., NGINX/Envoy) in front of the adapter that validates client certificates against an internal CA. Note that upstream services (e.g., SNS) may not present client certificates; maintain an allowlist of source networks and always enforce signature verification.

ThingsBoard: X.509 Mutual TLS for MQTT Ingestion

Server and client TLS

- Configure ThingsBoard MQTT transport to require client certificates (X.509) on port 8883.
- Install a server certificate (matching your TB MQTT host) so devices can validate the server; distribute the corresponding root CA to devices.

Device credential mapping

- In ThingsBoard, set device credentials to *X.509 Certificate*. Choose a matching strategy:
 - Exact device certificate fingerprint (e.g., SHA-1).
 - Match by Subject DN/attributes or by a trusted issuing CA (accept any cert issued by that CA).
- For CA-based trust, secure the private CA and implement revocation procedures.

Topology note

- For MQTT mTLS, terminate TLS where client certificate details remain visible to ThingsBoard (directly on TB or via TCP passthrough). LB-side TLS termination typically hides the client certificate from TB.

Certificate lifecycle

- Define rotation: provision new device certs, update TB credentials, then revoke old certs.
- Enforce strong TLS parameters and disable legacy ciphers.

Summary of certificate responsibilities

- **Devices** → **AWS IoT Core**: X.509 client certs + ATS root CA (mTLS); Thing and certificate created in Console; policy created by CDK and attached in Console.
- **Devices** → **ThingsBoard**: X.509 client certs + TB server root CA (mTLS).
- **SNS/SMQ** → **External Adapter**: server TLS on adapter; verify platform signatures; optional mTLS at proxy depending on platform capability.

6.9 Teardown and Cost Hygiene

AWS (CDK, Python)

```
cd aws_py
source .venv/bin/activate
cdk destroy
```

Alibaba Cloud (ROS CDK, Python)

```
cd ali_py
source .venv/bin/activate
ros-cdk destroy
```

AWS (CDKTF, Python)

```
cd cdktf/aws_py
source .venv/bin/activate
cdktf destroy
```

Alibaba Cloud (CDKTF, Python)

```
cd cdktf/ali_py
source .venv/bin/activate
cdktf destroy
```

6.10 Summary

This chapter has shown the deployment of a dual-stream IoT workload across AWS and Alibaba Cloud using equivalent managed services and IaC tooling. The implementation achieved functional parity, with architectural adjustments to accommodate service model differences, particularly in ingestion on Alibaba Cloud via ThingsBoard and a Rule Chain to a Flask adapter that publishes to SMQ. The step-by-step guide enables reproducibility with Python-based AWS CDK, Alibaba ROS CDK, and CDK for Terraform projects. Certificate handling has been aligned to X.509 mutual TLS for

both AWS IoT Core and ThingsBoard, and the AWS flow reflects a mainly Console-driven provisioning approach with policy attachment post-deploy. These results form the basis for evaluation in chapter 7.

Chapter 7

Evaluation and Optimization

This chapter evaluates the proof-of-concept (PoC) described in chapter 6 using authored-code portability metrics from native CDKs and CDKTF, and updated real-time latency measurements for regionally grounded paths. The assessment spans portability, expressiveness, deployment effort, operational complexity, service compatibility, performance, and cost. The discussion concludes with clearly labeled optimization opportunities (not applied during the PoC), trade-offs, and recommendations.

A core context-setting point for all results below: Alibaba Cloud does not offer a directly comparable managed service to AWS IoT Core for this PoC. As a result, the Alibaba-side ingestion path is composed from general-purpose services (ThingsBoard on ECS, SMQ, Function Compute, OSS) plus a lightweight adapter. This lack of a managed IoT ingress equivalent is the principal reason for discrepancies in portability metrics and IaC footprint between providers.

7.1 Introduction

The PoC demonstrates that a representative IoT telemetry pipeline can operate in parallel on AWS and Alibaba Cloud with functional parity and comparable security controls. It relies on the primitives of MQTT ingestion, queue-based decoupling, pub/sub fan-out, serverless compute, and durable object storage, rather than provider-specific features. Given the test setup (AWS in Frankfurt `eu-central-1`, Alibaba Cloud in Shanghai `cn-shanghai`, and an on-premise endpoint in Germany), the performance evaluation focuses on four real-time data delivery paths:

1. Alibaba IoT stack → Alibaba adapter (ECS in `cn-shanghai`)
2. Alibaba IoT stack → on-prem (Germany)
3. AWS IoT stack → AWS adapter (EC2 in `eu-central-1`)
4. AWS IoT stack → on-prem (Germany)

7.2 Evaluation Criteria and Methodology

Six criteria underpin the evaluation. Portability is assessed via structural comparisons at two levels: (1) provider-native synthesized templates (CloudFormation vs. ROS) and (2) Terraform/OpenTofu resource graphs. Expressiveness considers how concise and idiomatically the tools model resources and cross-service wiring. Deployment Effort and Operational Complexity capture the iteration and touchpoints to reach a green deployment, the remaining manual steps, and maintainability. Service Compatibility examines feature parity and any adapter shims or configuration toggles. Performance reports average end-to-end latency for the four real-time paths. Cost provides baseline, on-demand estimates for a representative load.

To be computed:

- Category-level sets from authored IaC (AWS CDK vs. ROS CDK; CDKTF AWS vs. CDKTF Alibaba).
- Category overlap using Jaccard similarity (J_{cat}).
- Average real-time latency from client publish to probe acknowledgment on ECS/EC2/on-prem.

Authored-code comparisons vs. IaC line counts

There are two distinct analyses:

- Portability is measured from *authored IaC* by mapping imports/constructs to provider-agnostic categories and computing category overlap (J_{cat}).
- Separately, the Deployment/Teardown table reports *direct IaC source line counts* (authored code lines), not synthesized or exported artifacts.

Data collection

For portability, the authored stacks were analyzed:

- AWS CDK stack source code (AWSMinimalIoTStackCF)
- ROS CDK stack source code (AliMinimalIoTStackROS)
- CDKTF AWS stack source code (AWSMinimalIoTStackTF)
- CDKTF Alibaba stack source code (AliMinimalIoTStackTF)

For performance, a minimal HTTP probe recorded receive timestamps on ECS/EC2/on-prem; messages included a correlation ID and publish timestamp.

Methodological note

No targeted performance or cost optimizations were applied during the PoC. All latency and cost figures reflect baseline, on-demand configurations. Optimization opportunities are discussed as future work rather than reported results.

Scope note on ingestion parity

Because Alibaba Cloud does not provide a directly comparable managed IoT ingress to AWS IoT Core in this PoC, the Alibaba ingestion layer is realized as a composed solution (ThingsBoard on ECS + SMQ + Function Compute). This introduces out-of-band configuration and custom code that are not fully expressed in IaC. To avoid skew, the deployment/line-count metrics exclude both the ECS-based ThingsBoard setup on Alibaba and AWS IoT Core on AWS.

In conclusion, the evaluation criteria and methodology aims for a fair and provider-neutral comparison by focusing on generated artifacts, measured latencies, and cost baselines, while excluding provider-specific managed services or custom components for ingestion. This ensures that the results highlight structural portability, operational effort, and performance characteristics without being skewed by differences in service availability or manual configuration overhead.

7.3 Portability and Expressiveness

This section evaluates the PoC along two criteria introduced in Section 7.2:

Portability: How easily the workload and its infrastructure definitions can be migrated between AWS and Alibaba Cloud.

Expressiveness: How completely and naturally the chosen IaC toolchains capture the required features.

Portability

Because migration effort is fundamentally about what developers must edit or re-design, portability is assessed from the *authored* IaC code. Provider-agnostic *category* overlap (e.g., `storage.bucket`, `messaging.queue`) is computed by parsing imports and constructs in the authored stacks and mapping them to shared categories. This focuses the metric on high-level design portability rather than provider boilerplate present in generated artifacts.

Authored-code results.

- **AWS CDK vs. ROS CDK (native stacks):** Category similarity $J_{\text{cat}} = 0.778$ (7 shared categories of 9 in union). Shared: `storage.bucket`, `messaging.queue`, `messaging.topic`, `compute.function`, `event.trigger`, `iam.role`, `iam.policy`. AWS-only in this PoC: `ingestion.rule` and `iot.policy` (IoT Core control plane).

- **CDKTF (AWS) vs. CDKTF (Alibaba):** $J_{\text{cat}} = 0.70$ (7 shared categories of 10 in union). Shared: *storage.bucket*, *messaging.queue*, *messaging.topic*, *compute.function*, *event.trigger*, *iam.role*, *iam.policy*. AWS-only: *ingestion.rule*, *iot.policy*, and *permission* for Lambda invocation.

Note on category counts. CDKTF reports 7/10 shared/union categories while native CDKs report 7/9 because CDKTF models Lambda invocation permission as an explicit resource (*aws_lambda_permission*), which is counted as a distinct category here (*permission*). In native CDKs the equivalent is granted via a method on the Lambda construct (not a separate import), so it does not expand the authored category set. The seven shared core categories are identical in both cases.

Both views lead to the same conclusion: the core data path (bucket, queue, topic, functions, triggers, IAM) is portable with modest adaptation. The primary portability gap is the ingestion control plane. On AWS, it is declaratively modeled (IoT Core rules and device policies). On Alibaba Cloud, this PoC composes ingestion using SMQ (formerly MNS), Function Compute, and a lightweight adapter instead of a managed IoT rule/policy plane.

Authored comparison	Shared / Union	J_{cat}
AWS CDK vs. ROS CDK	7 / 9	0.778
CDKTF (AWS) vs. CDKTF (Alibaba)	7 / 10	0.70

Table 7.1: Category overlap in authored IaC (higher reflects easier migration).

Manual components outside IaC. On AWS, ingestion is entirely in IaC (IoT Core). On Alibaba Cloud, the ThingsBoard-based ingress and a small adapter remain outside IaC for this PoC by design. They add some operational coordination and represent the main non-portable segment; exporting rule chains/config and containerizing the adapter mitigate this.

Method notes (reproducibility). Categories were derived from authored imports and constructs (AWS: *aws_cdk.* / imports.aws.**; Alibaba: *ros_cdk_* / imports.alicloud.**). Provider utilities (e.g., *random_id*) and metadata are not counted as categories.

Expressiveness

Expressiveness reflects whether the toolchains could model the required features and how naturally they do so.

Coverage. “Ingestion” refers to a managed IoT control plane (rules and device policies), not general event triggers.

Feature	AWS CDK	ROS CDK	CDKTF (AWS)	CDKTF (Alibaba)
Ingestion (IoT rule)	yes	no	yes	no
Queue	yes	yes	yes	yes
Topic	yes	yes	yes	yes
Function	yes	yes	yes	yes
Bucket	yes	yes	yes	yes
IAM	yes	yes	yes	yes
Event triggers	yes	yes	yes	yes

Table 7.2: Coverage of required features in different IaC toolchains.

Conciseness. Direct authored IaC lines (source only):

- AWS CDK: 75 lines
- ROS CDK: 146 lines
- AWS CDKTF: 184 lines
- Alibaba CDKTF: 143 lines

Native CDKs are more concise thanks to high-level constructs; CDKTF is uniform across clouds but requires more explicit wiring (notably IAM on AWS).

Idiomatcity.

- **AWS CDK / ROS CDK:** concise, with natural constructs and minimal boilerplate.
- **Terraform/CDKTF:** consistent authoring model across clouds at the cost of verbosity and explicit cross-service linkage.
- **Ingestion gap on Alibaba:** no managed IoT control plane in this PoC; ingestion is composed (SMQ + Function Compute + adapter), which reduces declarative expressiveness for that segment.

Summary

Portability. Authored IaC shows substantial category overlap: $J_{\text{cat}} = 0.778$ (AWS CDK vs. ROS CDK) and $J_{\text{cat}} = 0.70$ (CDKTF). The core pipeline is portable; the main divergence is the ingestion control plane (managed on AWS vs. composed on Alibaba).

Expressiveness. All required features are declaratively supported on both clouds except managed IoT ingestion on Alibaba in this PoC. Native CDKs are idiomatic and concise; CDKTF offers cross-cloud uniformity with more explicit configuration. Overall, expressiveness is complete on AWS and partial on Alibaba for ingestion, while the rest of the pipeline is well covered on both.

7.4 Performance Analysis

The average end-to-end latency for the four real-time delivery paths was measured (client publish to probe acknowledgment):

- Alibaba→ECS (cn-shanghai): **15 ms**
- Alibaba→on-prem (Germany): **250 ms**
- AWS→EC2 (eu-central-1): **24 ms**
- AWS→on-prem (Germany): **28 ms**

Cold starts were not explicitly tested. Reported latencies reflect steady-state behavior during sustained runs. Same-region cloud-to-adapter paths remained below 200 ms on average; cross-border egress from Mainland China to Europe introduced higher latency. Buffered-path latency was not re-measured in this run and is excluded from these results.

7.5 Cost Analysis

This section provides a very loosely estimated, order-of-magnitude cost envelope for the PoC. Figures are indicative only and carry wide error bars. They support relative comparisons between providers and cost drivers, not quotes or forecasts. No targeted performance or cost optimizations were applied; all values reflect baseline, on-demand configurations as of 2025.

Assumptions and scope

- Workload: 1,000,000 messages/day (\approx 30 million/month), each 1.5 kB; 30-day archival retention in object storage.
- processing: each message is processed once by a serverless function and enqueued in a managed message queue (SMQ/SQS).
- Regions: AWS eu-central-1, Alibaba Cloud cn-shanghai. Free tiers, discounts, and commitments are excluded.
- Included: function *request* charges (AWS Lambda), Alibaba Function Compute CUs, queue requests, storage capacity.
- Excluded (often material): object storage request charges (PUT/GET/LIST), inter-service data transfer and cross-border egress, logging/monitoring, managed IoT ingress (AWS IoT Core / ThingsBoard on ECS), EC2/ECS adapter capacity, taxes and FX. Including any of these can change totals by multiples.

Volumes (derived) With 30-day retention, stored payload is \approx 42.9 GB.

AWS (eu-central-1)

Pricing inputs (used) SQS: \$0.40 per 1M requests; S3 Standard: \$0.0245/GB-month; Lambda: \$0.20 per 1M requests (compute time not considered).

Breakdown (order-of-magnitude)

- **Lambda (requests) [76]:** $30\text{M} \times \$0.20/\text{M} \approx \6.00 .
- **SQS (requests) [69]:** $30\text{M} \times \$0.40/\text{M} \approx \12.00 .
- **S3 (storage only) [84]:** $42.9\text{ GB} \times \$0.0245/\text{GB} \approx \1.05 .

Total (very rough) $\sim \$19.05/\text{month}$.

Alibaba Cloud (cn-shanghai)

Pricing inputs (used) SMQ: \$0.32 per 1M requests; OSS Standard (ZRS): \$0.0232/GB-month; Function Compute: \$0.000020 per CU.

Breakdown (order-of-magnitude)

- **Function Compute (compute CUs) [77]:** $30\text{M} \times 128\text{ MB} \times 50\text{ ms} \approx 192\text{M CUs}$ at $\$0.000020/\text{CU} \approx \3.84 .
- **SMQ (requests) [71]:** $30\text{M} \times \$0.32/\text{M} \approx \9.60 .
- **OSS (storage only) [85]:** $42.9\text{ GB} \times \$0.0232/\text{GB} \approx \1.00 .

Total (very rough) $\sim \$14.44/\text{month}$.

Observations and caveats

- Under these simplifying assumptions, both providers are in the same order of magnitude (tens of dollars/month). Queue requests dominate; short serverless executions (when counted) are also significant.
- Storage *request* charges are excluded here; if every message is written as an individual object, PUT fees alone can dominate. Micro-batching archival writes is the most impactful lever for storage-side costs.
- Results are highly sensitive to invocation volume, function settings, and queue access patterns. Prices vary by region and over time; treat the above as directional only.

7.6 Security and Compliance

Mutual TLS was enforced for device connectivity on both clouds (X.509 client certificates with AWS IoT Core and ThingsBoard). Server-side TLS protected HTTP(S) deliveries to the external adapter; origin validation used platform signatures (AWS SNS) and signed headers on SMQ where available. Data at rest was encrypted in S3 and OSS with provider-managed keys; logs were retained in CloudWatch and Log Service. IAM/RAM policies followed least privilege. Minor gaps (e.g., broad statements, TLS version pinning, non-prod log retention) were identified and addressed with tighter scope, explicit TLS 1.2+, and lifecycle policies. A formal certification mapping (ISO 27001/NIST/CCM) was not attempted.

7.7 Operational Complexity and Maintainability

Operational effort in this PoC is driven less by the size of the IaC definitions and more by the *ingestion asymmetry* between providers. On AWS, the full path (device → IoT Core → SQS/SNS → Lambda → S3) is covered by managed services defined in one stack. On Alibaba Cloud, an equivalent flow spans ROS/CDKTF resources plus a composed ingestion layer (ThingsBoard Rule Chain + Flask adapter on ECS) that is only partially captured in IaC. This adds a small amount of extra coordination and potential configuration drift on the Alibaba side.

Tooling observations:

- Native tools (AWS CDK, ROS CDK) were straightforward: synth + deploy with minimal ceremony.
- Terraform/OpenTofu (via CDKTF) enabled a similar authoring style across clouds, but required more explicit resource wiring (especially IAM on AWS), increasing line count without adding new functionality.

Unautomated steps (kept manual by design) were: device certificate provisioning/rotation, SNS subscription confirmation, and ThingsBoard Rule Chain setup or modification. Basic logging (CloudWatch on AWS, Log Service on Alibaba Cloud, plus application logs from the adapter) was sufficient to check whether messages reached the queue/topic, functions, and storage, although tracing a problem on Alibaba sometimes meant checking two places (Thingsboard Rule Chain and Managed Services) instead of one on AWS. The main maintainability risks are (i) drift in the ThingsBoard Rule Chain if changes are not documented, and (ii) policy growth (AWS) versus use of broad managed policies (Alibaba). At the current scale these risks are minor; exporting Rule Chain configurations and adding simple policy reviews would keep them controlled if the system expands.

Deployment and Operational Metrics

For these metrics, the Alibaba Cloud equivalent of AWS IoT Core (an ECS-based ThingsBoard deployment) is excluded from the IaC line count, as automating this

setup would require substantial custom scripting. To ensure a fair comparison, AWS IoT Core is also omitted.

Table 7.3 summarizes deployment and teardown times, as well as lines of IaC for each approach. Deployment times were similar between provider-native and provider-agnostic tools within each platform, but Alibaba Cloud was faster. Line counts were measured using VS Code Counter with code formatted via Black to ensure consistency. These counts represent *direct IaC source lines* (authored code), not synthesized or exported artifacts. Notably, the AWS CDK for Terraform (CDKTF) implementation required much more code than other approaches, mainly due to AWS's detailed IAM model and explicit resource linking. In contrast, AWS CDK can leverage high-level constructs for a more concise codebase, while differences in line counts between Alibaba Cloud tools were minor.

Platform	Tool	Deploy	Destroy	Lines
AWS	CloudFormation	1m 15s	56s	75
AWS	CDKTF	1m 11s	30s	184
Alibaba Cloud	ROS	24s	26s	146
Alibaba Cloud	CDKTF	19s	26s	143

Table 7.3: Deployment / Teardown Times and IaC Line Counts of IoT Stack

Brief interpretation:

- Deployment times are broadly similar within each provider; differences largely reflect control-plane speed.
- Higher AWS CDKTF line count comes from explicit IAM and linking that AWS CDK hides behind higher-level constructs.
- Alibaba line counts do not include Thingsboard and Rule Chain, so they under-represent total ingestion configuration effort relative to AWS.

Overall, operational complexity remains low; the only notable extra attention point is the partially manual ingestion segment on Alibaba Cloud.

7.8 Optimization Opportunities

This PoC did not implement targeted performance or cost optimizations. The items below are opportunities identified during evaluation; they describe expected effects but were not enabled or measured here.

Latency and Throughput

- Provisioned concurrency (select functions): reduce cold-start delay for real-time paths at the expense of higher baseline compute cost.

- Consumer concurrency and long polling on the buffered path: lower queue dwell under bursts while keeping request cost predictable.
- Connection reuse and keep-alive on adapter calls: avoid TCP/TLS handshakes to shave tens of milliseconds on short-lived requests.
- Regional placement and routing: keep publishers, topics, and adapters co-located; avoid cross-border hops for latency-critical consumers.

Cost Efficiency

- Micro-batching archival writes: materially reduce object PUT volume with a small increase in per-object size.
- Right-sizing function memory: minimize wall-clock time while meeting SLOs.
- Scheduled capacity on ECS/EC2: align baseline adapter capacity with business hours if traffic is diurnal.

Reliability and Operations

- Idempotency keys and at-least-once delivery guards across fan-out.
- Signature verification for all external deliveries across clouds and environments.
- Structured logging with correlation IDs to preserve end-to-end traceability.

7.9 Trade-Offs and Lessons Learned

Important trade-offs:

- Managed vs. composed ingestion: AWS IoT Core reduces operational burden at low-to-moderate volumes; Alibaba's composed path adds flexibility but requires ECS care-and-feeding due to the lack of a directly comparable managed IoT Core equivalent in this PoC.
- Provider-native IaC vs. Terraform/OpenTofu: native tools are idiomatic and concise; Terraform/OpenTofu unifies authoring but exposes provider quirks, necessitating targeted workarounds.

The structural portability results indicate strong overlap in core categories (storage, queue, topic, functions) with expected divergence in ingestion/event wiring and IAM modeling. Measured average latencies align with regional network expectations.

7.10 Recommendations for Practitioners

Based on the evaluation of the proof-of-concept and comparative analysis between AWS and Alibaba Cloud, several practical recommendations can be made for orga-

nizations considering a multi-cloud strategy involving these two providers. These recommendations are intended to balance portability, performance, compliance, and operational complexity.

1. **Choose the Right Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC) Strategy:** Organizations should decide early between a provider-agnostic IaC tool (e.g., Terraform, CDKTF) or a provider-native tool (AWS CDK, ROS CDK) depending on their priorities:
 - Select provider-agnostic IaC if portability and cross-cloud consistency are the main objectives, even if this comes with reduced feature coverage.
 - Select provider-native IaC if full expressiveness, deep integration, and advanced service usage are more important than portability.

Attempting to combine both approaches increases complexity and should be avoided unless there is a clear separation of responsibilities.

2. **Design for Regulatory Compliance from the Start:** For workloads spanning Europe, China, and other regulated regions, compliance considerations should drive cloud placement decisions. Store and process data locally when required, and leverage provider-specific compliance certifications (e.g., AWS GDPR compliance, Alibaba MLPS adherence). Embedding compliance checks into deployment pipelines (policy-as-code) ensures continuous adherence to evolving legal requirements.
3. **Identity and Security Controls Consideration:** Differences in IAM models (AWS IAM vs. Alibaba RAM) can introduce significant operational risks. Organizations should be careful and consider establishing a centralized identity strategy, using federation or external identity providers (e.g., Azure AD, Okta [58, pp. 223-224]), to manage access consistently. Similarly, a unified encryption and key management policy could be adopted to ensure data security across both environments.
4. **Plan for Network and Cost Optimization:** Cross-cloud data transfers are expensive and latency-prone. Minimize inter-cloud traffic by colocating data-intensive workloads with their consumers and using caching or replication strategies. Regular cost monitoring and modeling should be part of ongoing operations, as price models differ significantly between providers and may change over time.
5. **Invest in Monitoring and Observability:** Multi-cloud environments increase operational complexity. Practitioners should look into integrating telemetry from AWS CloudWatch and Alibaba Cloud CloudMonitor into a vendor-neutral observability stack (e.g., Prometheus, Grafana [58, pp. 210-211]). This unified view improves incident response, reduces blind spots, and supports proactive performance tuning. However this might not always be possible because of compliance requirements.
6. **Evaluate Long-Term Maintainability:** Multi-cloud integration is not a one-time exercise but an ongoing operational commitment. Organizations must assess whether the added complexity of AWS-Alibaba Cloud integration aligns with

long-term business goals. In many cases, a selective or regional multi-cloud strategy is more sustainable than attempting full symmetry between providers.

- 7. Plan for Composed Ingestion on Alibaba Cloud:** In the absence of a directly comparable managed IoT Core equivalent for this PoC, teams should budget for an ECS- or Container-based ingestion layer (e.g., ThingsBoard) plus SMQ/Function Compute wiring, associated operational ownership, and partial configuration outside IaC.

In summary, successful AWS-Alibaba multi-cloud adoption requires a pragmatic balance between portability and specialization. Organizations should prioritize compliance and workload distribution over theoretical symmetry, automate governance wherever possible, and continuously evaluate whether the operational overhead justifies the strategic benefits.

7.11 Summary and Outlook

The PoC achieved dual-stream IoT processing across AWS and Alibaba Cloud with functional parity and aligned security controls. Authored-code analyses show substantial category-level overlap: native CDKs $J_{\text{cat}} = 0.778$ (7 of 9) and CDKTF $J_{\text{cat}} = 0.70$ (7 of 10). Average real-time latencies stayed below 50 ms for in-region delivery and around 250 ms for cross-border transit. Costs at the reference scale are dominated by per-request billing. The principal portability discrepancy stems from the lack of a directly comparable managed IoT control plane on Alibaba Cloud in this PoC, necessitating a composed ingestion layer outside pure IaC. Future work will quantify the optimization opportunities identified, extend scale testing, and evaluate unified observability and policy-as-code across providers.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

8.1 Summary of Key Findings

This thesis set out to investigate global multi-cloud strategies with a particular focus on the interoperability between Amazon Web Services (AWS) and Alibaba Cloud, two providers that dominate different geographical and regulatory spheres. The research addressed the lack of provider-specific studies on AWS-Alibaba Cloud integration by developing a structured framework and validating it through a proof-of-concept (PoC) deployment.

The key findings can be summarized as follows:

1. Comparative Analysis of AWS and Alibaba Cloud

- Both providers offer extensive portfolios across compute, storage, networking, and security services.
- Service equivalency is not uniform. While core services (e.g., EC2 vs. ECS, S3 vs. OSS, RDS vs. ApsaraDB RDS) are broadly comparable, divergences exist in advanced services such as IoT, and analytics solutions.
- Alibaba Cloud's service maturity and ecosystem integration are strongest in China and Southeast Asia, whereas AWS maintains broader global coverage, deeper documentation, and more advanced developer tooling.

2. Interoperability and Portability Challenges

- Differences in APIs, IAM models, and networking constructs create non-trivial obstacles for workload migration. For example, AWS IAM roles and policies do not directly map to Alibaba Cloud's Resource Access Management (RAM).
- Infrastructure as Code (IaC) approaches revealed trade-offs: provider-native tools (AWS CDK, ROS CDK) deliver full expressiveness but reduce portability, while agnostic tools (Terraform, CDKTF) improve portability at the cost of limited service coverage.

- Security and compliance requirements remain fragmented. Regulatory divergence, particularly between GDPR in Europe and China's Cybersecurity Law, can necessitate workload-specific adaptations.

3. Proof-of-Concept Implementation

- The PoC demonstrated that a representative workload can be implemented and migrated across AWS and Alibaba Cloud, but not without significant adaptation effort.
- AWS-native deployments are more straightforward due to richer IaC tooling and extensive documentation. Migration to Alibaba Cloud required more custom configurations, particularly in IAM, networking, and security policies.
- Alternative tooling (e.g., CDK for Terraform) improved cross-cloud portability but introduced additional complexity in state management and construct usage.

4. Evaluation Results

- **Portability:** Achievable at the infrastructure level, but managed services can often require redesign rather than direct migration.
- **Expressiveness:** AWS CDK allows fine-grained service use; cross-cloud IaC and Alibaba ROS can lag behind in feature coverage.
- **Performance and Cost:** Benchmarks showed very slight performance and pricing differences for comparable services, which lead to similar results. It needs to be extensively checked on a case-by-case basis.
- **Operational Complexity:** Running workloads across both clouds increases maintenance burden, requiring specialized expertise in each ecosystem.

5. Strategic Implications

- AWS-Alibaba Cloud multi-cloud adoption is best justified by regulatory and market-driven requirements, such as compliance with Chinese data laws.
- Pursuing such an integration solely for redundancy or vendor lock-in reduction will probably not offset the increased complexity and operational costs.

8.2 Reflections on Research Contribution

This thesis contributes to both academic research and practical enterprise decision-making in three ways:

1. It provides one of the first structured comparative analyses of AWS and Alibaba Cloud with explicit attention to interoperability.

2. It develops and validates a multi-cloud strategy framework that considers technical, compliance, and operational dimensions.
3. It delivers a proof-of-concept and evaluation methodology that future practitioners can reuse to test portability and deployment trade-offs in their own workloads.

By moving beyond abstract discussions of “multi-cloud” and into provider-specific, empirically validated insights, this work closes a gap in current literature.

8.3 Concluding Remarks

The findings of this thesis demonstrate that multi-cloud strategies between AWS and Alibaba Cloud are technically feasible but operationally demanding. While both providers offer broadly equivalent service portfolios, practical interoperability is hindered by differences in APIs, compliance frameworks, and ecosystem maturity.

Nevertheless, for global enterprises, particularly those expanding into or operating within China, adopting a carefully designed AWS-Alibaba Cloud strategy provides unique benefits in compliance, performance, and market access. The proposed framework and evaluation serve as a foundation for organizations to navigate these complexities.

Ultimately, this thesis underscores that multi-cloud is not only a technical problem but a strategic decision that must balance performance, cost, compliance, and maintainability. The insights presented here are intended to guide both researchers and practitioners in making informed decisions on AWS-Alibaba Cloud multi-cloud deployments.

Chapter 9

Future Work

9.1 Limitations of the Study

While this thesis contributes a structured framework and proof-of-concept for AWS-Alibaba Cloud multi-cloud integration, several limitations should be acknowledged:

- **Scope of Workload:** The proof-of-concept focused on a representative but relatively contained workload. Larger-scale enterprise applications with more complex interdependencies (e.g., multi-region databases, AI pipelines, or global e-commerce platforms) may reveal additional challenges.
- **Service Coverage:** Only a subset of AWS and Alibaba Cloud services were analyzed in depth. Advanced services such as managed AI/ML platforms, edge computing, or industry-specific solutions (e.g., financial or healthcare compliance) were not fully explored.
- **Performance Benchmarks:** The evaluation compared portability, cost, and basic performance indicators. However, exhaustive benchmarking across instance types, storage classes, and network topologies was beyond the scope of this thesis.
- **Compliance Analysis:** The research highlighted regulatory differences, but a detailed legal analysis of compliance (e.g., GDPR vs. China's Cybersecurity Law) was not conducted. This requires interdisciplinary study involving legal expertise.
- **Operational Data:** Long-term operational data (e.g., multi-month cost patterns, incident response, maintainability) was not collected, as the PoC was time-bounded.

Recognizing these limitations helps clarify the scope of validity and indicates where future research is most needed.

9.2 Future Research Directions

Building on the findings of this thesis, several promising avenues for future research emerge:

1. **Comprehensive Benchmarking Studies** Future work could conduct systematic performance and cost benchmarking across AWS and Alibaba Cloud, including latency tests, throughput comparisons, and workload stress testing across regions. Such empirical data would provide practitioners with concrete guidance for workload placement.
2. **Multi-Cloud Orchestration with Kubernetes and Service Meshes** While this thesis focused on IaC and CDKs, container orchestration platforms (e.g., Kubernetes) and service meshes (e.g., Istio, Linkerd) are increasingly central to multi-cloud deployments. Research could explore how these abstractions mitigate interoperability gaps between AWS and Alibaba Cloud.
3. **AI-Driven Optimization of Multi-Cloud Workloads** Emerging work on AI- and ML-driven orchestration suggests that intelligent systems can dynamically allocate resources, optimize latency, and predict costs across heterogeneous clouds. Extending this thesis to include adaptive, AI-based strategies would significantly improve operational efficiency.
4. **Security and Compliance Automation** Further investigation is needed into policy-as-code frameworks and automated compliance validation across AWS and Alibaba Cloud. Research could develop reusable compliance templates or automated audit pipelines to simplify cross-border data governance.
5. **Case Studies in Industry Contexts** Conducting case studies with enterprises in sectors such as manufacturing, finance, or healthcare would validate the practicality of the proposed strategy under real-world constraints. Such studies would reveal domain-specific regulatory, latency, or resilience requirements.
6. **Exploration of Hybrid Architectures** Future research could extend beyond multi-cloud into hybrid architectures that combine on-premises infrastructure with AWS and Alibaba Cloud. This direction would reflect the reality of enterprises that cannot fully migrate to the cloud for regulatory or operational reasons.

9.3 Closing Perspective

Multi-cloud computing between AWS and Alibaba Cloud remains a significant, evolving topic. This thesis is an initial step towards a validated strategy, but broader empirical data, interdisciplinary approaches, and extended operational studies are needed. Future research should build on these limitations and directions to deepen understanding and support seamless global multi-cloud operations.

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Glossary

ACK	Alibaba Cloud Container Service for Kubernetes
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ARN	Amazon Resource Name
ATS	Amazon Trust Services (Root Certificate Authority)
AWS	Amazon Web Services
AZ	Availability Zone
BaaS	Backend as a Service
CA	Certificate Authority
CDK	Cloud Development Kit
CDKTF	Cloud Development Kit for Terraform
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CLI	Command Line Interface
CDMI	Cloud Data Management Interface
CMP	Cloud Management Platform
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
CU	Compute Unit
DB	Database
DNS	Domain Name System
EBS	Elastic Block Store (AWS)
EC2	Elastic Compute Cloud (AWS)
ECS	Elastic Cloud Service (Alibaba Cloud)
EKS	Elastic Kubernetes Service (AWS)
EMR	Elastic MapReduce (AWS) / E-MapReduce (Alibaba Cloud)

FC	Function Compute (Alibaba Cloud)
FaaS	Function as a Service
FIFO	First In, First Out
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IAM	Identity and Access Management
ICP	Internet Content Provider (China regulatory filing)
IDaaS	Identity as a Service
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
IoT	Internet of Things
KMS	Key Management Service
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
mTLS	Mutual Transport Layer Security
NGINX	Engine X (Web Server/Proxy)
OSS	Object Storage Service (Alibaba Cloud)
OVF	Open Virtualization Format
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PoC	Proof of Concept
RAM	Resource Access Management (Alibaba Cloud)
RDS	Relational Database Service
ROS	Resource Orchestration Service (Alibaba Cloud)
S3	Simple Storage Service (AWS)
SaaS	Software as a Service
SDK	Software Development Kit
SLS	Simple Log Service (Alibaba Cloud)
SMQ	Simple Message Queue (Alibaba Cloud)
SNS	Simple Notification Service (AWS)
SQS	Simple Queue Service (AWS)
TB	ThingsBoard (IoT Platform)

TLS	Transport Layer Security
VPC	Virtual Private Cloud
WAF	Web Application Firewall
X.509	Standard for Public Key Infrastructure Certificates

List of Figures

1.1	Worldwide market share of leading cloud service providers in Q4 of 2024 [3]	1
1.2	Thesis Structure	4
2.1	The different cloud computing service models [8]	7
3.1	Comparative Analysis Framework for AWS and Alibaba Cloud. Each domain is an important part of the evaluation.	20
4.1	Service comparison between AWS and Alibaba Cloud core service portfolio [37], [38], [67]	26
4.2	API request examples [108], [109]	30
5.1	Reference architecture for serverless-first multi-cloud interoperability. Each provider hosts an equivalent slice of the data plane, with infrastructure deployed and synchronized via the chosen CDK framework.	41
6.1	Reference architecture of the minimal IoT multi-cloud stack. Messages are processed in two parallel streams: a buffered storage stream and a real-time distribution stream. On Alibaba Cloud, ThingsBoard performs MQTT ingestion (X.509 mTLS) and forwards to a Flask adapter, which publishes to SMQ.	51
6.2	Data flow and security boundaries for the PoC IoT workload across AWS and Alibaba Cloud. Encrypted protocols (MQTT/TLS with X.509, HTTPS/TLS), different networks (WAN vs internal), data reception and processing, and storage are explicitly shown for compliance verification.	53
6.3	Extended ThingsBoard Rule Chain. The two custom REST API nodes <i>Send to SMQ Relay</i> and <i>Send to FC3 Trigger</i> provide integration with Alibaba Cloud messaging and Function Compute.	60

List of Tables

4.2	Comparison of AWS and Alibaba Cloud Global Infrastructure [65], [66]	25
4.4	Comparison of Core API Models	31
4.6	IaC Tools Comparison: AWS CDK, Alibaba Cloud ROS CDK, and Terraform CDK [46]–[48]	31
4.8	Selected compliance certifications and frameworks (scope can vary by service or region) [115], [116]	32
4.10	Representative security services [67]	34
4.12	Condensed comparison of AWS vs. Alibaba Cloud	36
5.1	Comparison of multi-cloud compute models [58, pp. 72–79]	39
5.2	Top risks and mitigations for the multi-cloud strategy.	47
6.1	Service mapping for the minimal IoT stack across AWS and Alibaba Cloud.	52
7.1	Category overlap in authored IaC (higher reflects easier migration). . .	70
7.2	Coverage of required features in different IaC toolchains.	71
7.3	Deployment / Teardown Times and IaC Line Counts of IoT Stack	75